

Chinese manufacturing companies' role in the national transition towards sustainable industry

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Abstract

This research aimed to explore the role of Chinese manufacturing companies in the national transition towards sustainable industry, innovations, and infrastructure, in keeping with SDG9 goals. The research was based on case study research as the research strategy. Data for the sectoral research was collected using document analysis. The Institutional Theory was applied to explore why China's manufacturing enterprises should give in to coercive pressures and normative pressures to improve their unit labour output. It also helped demonstrate why giving in to both normative and coercive pressures will enable the country to perfect their standard systems of industrialization as well as leverage its enterprises' innovative capacity to ensure a smooth and speedy transition to sustainable industry, innovations, and infrastructure. The dimensions of institutional theory, such as mimetic pressures and conventional pressures, also helped explore how the rural digital infrastructure can enable the country's rural manufacturing sector to facilitate a faster transition to SDG9. It is established in this research that heightened collective coercive pressure from the Chinese government and external environmental standardisation agencies reduce conflicts in social and economic logic, thus lowering the propensity for Chinese manufacturing enterprises to delay the transition to a sustainable industry 4.0. Heightened mimetic pressure from increased competition for sustainable products in the international market has also reduced the propensity for Chinese manufacturing enterprises to delay the transition to a sustainable industry 4.0. Heightened normative pressure through education and training is also found to have increased the social logic and reduced the propensity for Chinese manufacturing enterprises to concentrate on profit logic. For China to fully digitize the rural manufacturing sector in order to meet the targets for SDG9, there will be a need to rely substantially on coercive pressures to effect positive changes like improving digital infrastructure and education.

Keywords: Sustainable development, Industry 4.0, Chinese manufacturing industry, sustainable industry, sustainable industry, innovations, and infrastructure.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

The conception of “Industry 4.0,” or fourth industrial revolution, became popular after the Hannover Industrial Expo of 2011, where it was fronted as referring to “the development of “cyber-physical systems” (CPS) and dynamic data processes that use massive amounts of data to drive smart machines” in the manufacturing sector (Feng et al., 2018). Also known as intelligent manufacturing, Industry 4.0 has in the last decade formed the mainstay of economic policies of countries globally that seek to encourage investment in the upgrading and transformation of domestic industries. China has not been an exception) (Shao, 2017) (Xu & Lin, 2015; Lasi et al., 2014). While the growth of the country’s sustainable manufacturing industry looks promising, it is still unclear how the outcomes of the plans actually will turn out to be. Currently, China’s renewable energy capacity is the highest globally, generating close to 289 gigawatts (GW) from both wind and solar plants annually, in comparison to that of the United States, which is estimated to be 121 GW. Nevertheless, China only managed to generate 38% more electricity compared to the US in 2017. There are concerns that this discrepancy could be because of general inefficiencies and poor quality of equipment used by Chinese manufacturers (Li et al., 2018).

In reality, the Chinese manufacturing industry is in a transitional period towards sustainability. Currently, there are strong indications that the industry may no longer be a prime location for low-cost manufacturing (Industry Insights, 2018). On the contrary, besides emphasis on investment in sustainable industry, the Chinese manufacturing industry is going through rapid evolution into a high-tech industry. In 2018, President Xi Jinping emphasized this ideal by stating that “we should pursue innovation-driven development and intensify cooperation in frontier areas such as digital economy, artificial intelligence, nanotechnology and quantum computing, and advance the development of big data, cloud computing and smart cities so as to turn them into a digital silk road of the 21st century” (Industry Insights, 2018).

An exploration of the current situation of China indicates that the country currently accelerating its green manufacturing initiatives. In June 2018, Shanghai made public the city’s plans to encourage the adoption of green manufacturing initiatives with the view of moving toward a highly sustainable industrial environment (Carey, 2018). Focus was placed on reducing carbon emissions, energy efficiency, and mitigation of environmental impacts of manufacturing. By 2020, Shanghai had set up at least 20 green industrial parks, 10 green supply chains, and 100 green factories (Carey, 2018). Beijing also announced the city’s plans for sustainable industry in 2018, and committed to shut down more than 1,000 manufacturing firms in keeping with the need to reduce smog. Indeed, as of 2018, Beijing had either closed down or relocated some 2,470 traditional manufacturing plants (Carey, 2018). Such sustainable manufacturing initiatives are components of a larger plan designed to put China as a major manufacturing country worldwide, while at the same time enabling the country to join the global transition to sustainable economy. Because of the growing scarcity of

cheap labor and a growth of vicious competition in the sphere of industrial robotics, the country seeks to launch its dominance in sustainable technologies, automation, robotics, and artificial intelligence (AI).

1.2 Research problem

Efforts for national transition towards sustainable industry, innovations, and infrastructure have been problematic in China. Challenges to a successful transition form the basis of this research. China has had to contend with a range of challenges in the attempt to transition towards Industry 4.0 that is largely characterized by sustainable industry, innovations and infrastructure (Carey, 2018). The country's manufacturing sector currently confronts challenges such as underdeveloped innovative capacity, defective standard systems of industrialization, low added value, wasteful labour output per unit, poorly constructed digital infrastructure, high rates of air and water pollution, and high energy consumption. Nevertheless, the country's manufacturing sector plays a vital role in the country's economy. In the period 2009-2015, the manufacturing industry made up nearly 30 percent of the country's GDP. This indicates the urgency with which emphasis should be placed on advancing the industry's capacity in line with Industry 4.0 concept (Yang, 2013; Xu & Lin, 2015).

In reality, China's industry 4.0 systems are still at an early stage when put side by side with those of developed countries like Germany. The rapid transition to industry 4.0 in Germany is strongly linked to successful measures by the government to provide policy and funding support for enabling R&D alliances as well as a kind of industry that is strongly rooted in collaborative research between research units, universities, customers, and the manufacturing industry (Schumpeter, 2002; Freeman, 1987; Khan & ManopichetwattanaV, 1989). As a consequence, a range of alliance systems are set up by major, research institutions, enterprises and higher learning institutions that have strong research capabilities. The success of such R&D alliances has been central to the realization of a full mobilization of resources to facilitate innovation and development of key technologies. Such technologies are enabling a realization of intelligent manufacturing industry and promoting the creation and development of talent system (Zhao & Liu, 2016; Yang, 2013, Sailer, 2014; Shao, 2017; Xu & Lin, 2015).

Additionally, unlike China, Germany has come up with sets of comprehensive plans and in the process set up "standardization systems." For instance, Germany developed the first standardized roadmap of industry 4.0 in the world in December 2013 (Sailer, 2014). This has enabled the interconnection and intercommunication between enterprises, resources, machines, and people. Presently, the Chinese manufacturing industry features differing levels of automatization and informationization. While there is a variety of industrial intelligent software that are currently implemented, a lack of standardization has meant that production facilities and equipment are not compatible with each other (Zhao & Liu, 2016; Yang, 2013, Sailer, 2014; Shao, 2017; Xu & Lin, 2015).

1.3 Research rationale

There is significant rationale to explore mechanisms for addressing challenges to a successful national transition to sustainable industry, innovations and infrastructure in China. Addressing such challenges will speed up the national transition to Industry 4.0. Current evidence from China's manufacturing industry shows

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that the industry faces a number of problems related to the manufacturing sector, under the backdrop of Industry 4.0 (Zhao & Liu, 2016; Yang, 2013, Sailer, 2014; Shao, 2017; Xu & Lin, 2015). Inefficient unit labour output remains a major barrier to the transition, owing to growing concerns over insufficient manufacturing technology (Zhao & Liu, 2016).

Concerns also abound on the issue of high imperfection of standard systems of industrialization. For the country to transition smoothly to sustainable industry, innovations and infrastructure, it may need to develop a set of standard systems that can facilitate information system integrations among diverse manufacturing firms. However, studies are yet to exhaustively investigate the role of perfecting standard systems of industrialization in the attempt to transition to Industry 4.0 (Lasi et al., 2014)

China's relatively weak innovative capacity and insufficiency of core talents, compared to developed countries like China, is another major challenge delaying the transition to sustainable industry, innovations and infrastructure, under the broad spectrum of Industry 4.0. Innovative capacity has strongly been associated with R&D investment, where China lags behind the global average (Li & Liu, 2011; Xu & Lin, 2015; Zhao & Liu, 2016). This is in spite of the fact that the current competition between economic strength and the market is biased towards a nation's innovative capacity. There is a need to investigate how China's innovative capacity can be leveraged to ensure a smooth and speedy transition to sustainable industry, innovations, and infrastructure.

China's manufacturing industry also needs to face up to its underdeveloped digital infrastructure, which also delays the national transition to Industry 4.0 (Sailer, 2014). Yet, it still remains unclear how the country's digital infrastructure could be developed to facilitate a speedy transition. In effect, while the country's network system has been originally built, the rapidity of the networks developed is far behind that of countries that have transitioned to industry 4.0, such as Germany. For instance, internet penetration is still comparatively low, particularly in rural areas, where it is estimated to be 42.5%. The rural areas are also disadvantaged because of relatively underdeveloped transportation infrastructure (Xu & Lin, 2015; Shao, 2017). Such concerns have been underscored in research as capable of enabling a speedy transition to industry 4.0. The manner in which digital infrastructure will enable the rural manufacturing sector in China to transition to sustainable industry, innovations, and infrastructure is yet to be conclusively outlined in research (Lasi et al., 2014; Zhao & Liu, 2016).

High incidences of environmental pollution are also linked to challenges to a successful transition to a sustainable industry. Research demonstrates that the country's industrial structure is incapable of meeting sustainable development needs. In particular, the manufacturing enterprises that contribute to high incidences of pollution are high energy consumers (Manufacturing Consultants, 2021). While China has put up sustainable initiatives, it still remains the largest carbon emitter in the world with as much as 9,040 million metric tons annually. This is equivalent to 28% global fuel combustion, in comparison to the United States, which emits roughly 4,997 metric tons per a num. In 2015, nearly 1.8 million people in the country died from complications that arose from environmental pollution (Carey, 2018). This also provides justifications to investigate how environmental pollution has challenged successful transition to a sustainable industry and recommends strategies for improving the country's industrial structure to enable it to meet Goal 9 of the SDG.

1.4 Research aim and objectives

The aim of this research is to explore the role of Chinese manufacturing companies in the national transition towards sustainable industry, innovations, and infrastructure, in keeping with Sustainable

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Development Goals (SDG). In effect, SDG9 promotes sustainable and ecologically produced goods, and offer additional value to Industry 4.0 systems, which relate to a reduction of pollution, overconsumption of materials, and poor recycling. The approach applied is based on institutional theory, which is applied to identify and analyze factors promoting the survival and legitimacy of manufacturing enterprises' practices that can support national transition towards SDG9. In keeping with the research aim, the study made five key research questions the basis of this paper's investigation:

- How can Chinese manufacturers develop the unit labour output through science and technology in order to facilitate national transition to sustainable industry, innovations, and infrastructure?
- How can the manufacturing industry leverage standard systems of industrialization to facilitate the national transition to SDG9?
- What mechanisms can improve China's innovative capacity to ensure a smooth and speedy transition to sustainable industry, innovations, and infrastructure?
- What role can the digitization of China's rural manufacturing sector play in facilitating national transition to sustainable industry, innovations, and infrastructure?
- What strategies could improve China's industrial structure to speed up the realization of SDG9?

1.5 Research Significance

The results of the study will justify the urgency with which emphasis should be placed on advancing the industry's capacity in line with Industry 4.0 concept. The study will also provide data for reviewing the Chinese manufacturing industry's Industry 4.0 growth potential. Because of the rapidly growing Chinese economy and the increasingly expanding consumer market, there is a need to show the Chinese domestic manufacturing industry's growth potential and why emphasis should be placed on transition to Industry 4.0 and meeting SDG goal 9. Hence, the study provides recommendations for improving the country's industrial structure in the attempt to realize SDG9.

The results of the study will contribute to research knowledge on how the Chinese manufacturing industry can develop the unit labor output through science and technology in order to facilitate national transition towards sustainable industry, innovations and infrastructure. It will also close knowledge gaps on the role of standard systems of industrialization, innovative capacity, and digital infrastructure in national transition to Industry 4.0.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Effects of manufacturers' unit labour outputs on transition to Industry 4.0

A number of approaches have been used in scholarly research to define and characterise urban economic sustainability (Yang, 2013, Sailer, 2014; Shao, 2017). For instance, the United Nations Commission on Sustainable Development (CSD) has tended to measure sustainable economic development using themes like patterns of production, economic development, and economic structures (Li et al. 2018). Basically, economic growth can be determined by looking at the balance of trade, share of investment in GDP, and GDP per capita

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(Sailer, 2014; Shao, 2017; Xu & Lin, 2015).. With respect to patterns of production and patterns of consumption, the cost and efficiency of resource usage are often taken into perspective. In recent years, studies have looked at a tendency of manufacturing firms to either upgrade or diversify their production with focus on economic sustainability. In turn, diversity and industrial upgrading have been treated in research as long-term fundamental factors that have a potential to strengthen economic sustainability (Li et al. 2018).

According to Li et al (2018), the process of industry upgrading to ensure sustainable economic development presents an effective approach for improving the efficiency of production processes, reduction of carbon emissions, and energy saving. Related studies have also linked low-carbon industries to green industries. Li et al (2018) also established a strong relationship between upgrading of industrial structure and optimising of space. They also found that industrial diversity has a positive effective on economic growth and reduction of unemployment. This demonstrates a link between industrial diversity and economic resilience (Zhao & Liu, 2016; Yang, 2013).

Across the research, there is an understanding that labour productivity is the most actively used measure of productivity, as it measures the extent to which human inputs are put into use to generate outputs (Bakkari and Khatory. 2017; De Man et al., 2017; Gerlitz, 2016). In the manufacturing sector, labour productivity is basically output over input. Labour input is measured in hours worked. On the other hand, output is measured in units.

The United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO) also acknowledges the significance of skills development as major driver of Industry 4.0. In this respect, UNIDO (2017) observed the need for manufacturing enterprises to undergo a pro-active skills transformation with emphasis on shaping the young generation to be “robotic natives” in order to meet the skills requirements for industry 4.0. UNIDO’s argument is well supported in extent research, which emphasises that inclusive and sustainable industrial development (ISID) can only be met by players in the manufacturing sector who transform their workforce into digital natives who can coexist and collaborate with intelligent machines (Beier et al., 2018; Gabriel and Pessl, 2016).

When it comes to transition to Industry 4.0, questions have been raised over the quality of labour productivity that could be facilitative to it realization. According to García-Muiña et al. (2020), manufacturers’ unit labour outputs can only facilitate a national transition towards industry 4.0 when they invest in human capital with advanced technological knowhow. Indeed, to ensure this, manufacturing enterprises acknowledge the implications of industry 4.0 technologies on improved production processes in ways that are more efficient and less adversely impactful on the environment. Yet, their major concern is access to a highly skilled labour to meet the technological knowledge gaps needed for industry 4.0 (Machado et al, (2019).

A number of studies have explained the reason for this. According to Beier et al. (2018), a sustainable transition process to industry 4.0 should intrinsically be dependent on the effective operational introduction of sustainability practices. However, the process should not discount the strategic evolution of manufacturing enterprises with respect to leveraging a highly technological advanced labour to facilitate value creation (Shao, 2017; Sailer, 2014; Yang, 2014). In their study of manufacturing enterprises in the United States, García-Muiña et al. (2020) observed that the process of implementing sustainability is characteristically a complex process requiring a medium-long-term strategic vision, effective communication between business units and the executive management, as well as the level of employee competence and quality of their productivity.

In a related study by UNCTAD (2019), observations were made to the effect that since industry 4.0 characteristically consists of a more concentrated utility of automation and data exchange in manufacturing leading to smart and connected production systems, manufacturing enterprises must acquire a highly relevant technologically competent labour. According to UNCTAD (2019), this would be realistic given that at the centre of industry 4.0 is the increased level of digitization to manufacture products by means of connectivity, big data collection, and analytics, the industrial Internet of things, greater human and machine interaction, and increased use of three-dimensional (3D) printing and robotics. In the study, UNCTAD (2019) observed that the US manufacturing sector currently acknowledges the unit impact of a highly relevant labor output to facilitate the national transition towards sustainable Industry 4.0 owing to the complexity of frontier technologies associated with Industry 4.0. As a result, the few large manufacturing enterprises in the United States that dominate the market of frontier technologies like the Internet of things, and artificial intelligence have concentrated on employing technologically advanced labour force to facilitate the transition (García-Muiña et al, 2020).

This indicates that manufacturing enterprises' capacity to adopt and adapt to the high-tech Industry 4.0 is contingent on the technological capability of their workforce. UNCTAD (2019) observed that since more manufacturers in the developed countries are focusing on employees that can fill the knowledge gap towards transitioning to sustainable industry 4.0, countries will also be forced to invest in education policies that can improve their technological capabilities (Schumpeter, 2002; Freeman, 1987). Therefore, as much as manufacturers have considered the value of upgrading their capabilities by hiring a skilled workforce with high technological knowhow, policymakers should also play their role in coming up with education policies to develop digital skills and literacy (Machado et al, 2019).

Evidence for this trend is provided in an industry report by Deloitte (2018), which showed that globally, many manufacturers are upgrading their workforce to address the existing variance between skills and employer needs, which is a major threat to the realization of a sustainable Industry 4.0. Deloitte (2018) underscored that while millions of the youth today are either underemployed or unemployed, manufacturers have jobs that cannot be filled because of existing skills gaps. Such a reality has prompted manufacturing enterprises to recognize their role in facilitating the realization of a sustainable industry 4.0 by recruiting a workforce that can operate digital technologies and physical assets. For this reason, manufacturing enterprises are contributing to the realization of United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through their workforce restructuring efforts.

In the case of Thailand, manufacturing enterprises have demonstrated an increased awareness of the need to upgrade their workforce capability in order to take advantage of interconnected set of factors like technological advancements, highly fragmented production systems, and rapidity of innovation to address tectonic changes (Baxter, 2017). In their study, Baxter (2017) remarked that manufacturers can only meet the work targets identified in the United Nations' 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development by integrating "forward-thinking, fully respect fundamental principles, and rights at work" into their employment policies to stimulate national transition to industry 4.0 without contributing to environmental damage. Abramova and Grishchenko's (2020) study of the Russian manufacturing industry also confirms the continued significance of manufacturers' unit labour outputs in facilitating national transition towards sustainable Industry 4.0. Abramova and Grishchenko (2020) investigated the relationship between labour productivity and employment, and technological advancements in manufacturing industries in Russia. They found that labour

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productivity and employment and technological advancements have a fragmentary relationship, yet are both significant for the realization of industry 4.0 in Russia. While the researchers did not find a strong link between technological advancements and labour productivity, they concluded that the relationship between the two variables could indeed be possible when labour productivity is upgraded to fill existing skills gap. In their study, Abramova and Grishchenko (2020) failed to observe a significant change in the number of employees or labour productivity as a result of investment in ICT and concluded that this could exemplify the social (employment) stability and economic (labour productivity) in the manufacturing industry.

Therefore, in spite of the prevailing stereotypes regarding a decline in employment rates and a rise in labour productivity due to investment in technology, their findings suggested smooth and fragmentary changes (García-Muiña et al., 2020). In light of this finding, they explained that Russia is yet to accumulate a critical mass for the extension of ICTs to substantially influence national transition to sustainable industry 4.0 because of existing skills gaps, specifically in the manufacturing industry. Accordingly, Abramova and Grishchenko (2020) suggest that manufacturers' unit labour outputs could indeed play a critical role of facilitating the national transition towards sustainable Industry 4.0 by closing impending skills gap. The researchers elaborated that ICTs require extensive periods of time to attain maturity, specifically if the process of closing the necessary skills gap needed to ensure labour productivity growth are taken into advantage (Abramova and Grishchenko, 2020). In other words, as much as manufacturing enterprises in Russia need to significantly invest in requisite innovations to attain sustainable industry 4.0, this would critically depend on the quality of labour needed for the national transition. Abramova and Grishchenko (2020) provided a credible explanation for this. In their view, while technological advancements and investment in technological innovation affect a variety of environmental, economic, and social dimensions of manufacturing enterprises' sustainability, they need a technologically knowledgeable labour that can advance business processes and product quality using such innovations to deliver sustainable benefits.

2.2 Effects of manufacturing industry-standard systems on transition to Industry 4.0

Across the manufacturing industry-standard research, emphasis has been placed on the role of standardisation system in enabling national transition to industry 4.0 (Beier et al., 2018; Cerri et al., 2016; Ferrera et al, 2017). The question of industry standards has, in particular, been emphasized by the United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO), which acknowledges that a transition to sustainable Industry 4.0 technologies can only be attained once individual technologies, formats, and interfaces are standardised. According to UNIDO (2017), there is an absolute need to consolidate new concepts through consensus-based standardization at initial stages of technological innovation prior to being adopted in manufacturing activities globally.

UNIDO's (2017) remarks have been echoed in research efforts and industry practices globally. In Germany, for instance, a proposition has been made for neutral reference architecture known as RAMI 4.0, which is expected to set up an inclusive framework for conceptualizing and developing structural designs for Industry 4.0 systems (UNIDO, 2017). In which case, there is a need to accelerate new standards that can enable or facilitate the acceleration of new Industrial revolution (NIR). UNIDO (2017) explains that this could be attained by making sure that new standards are developed that can be pursued by various countries. While this has been cited as potentially a challenge for international standardization authorities owing to the high number of innovations emerging from various countries globally, ensuring that national standardization

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activities are appropriately harmonized with those that are at the international level is the only way in which sustainability can be achieved (Abramova & Grishchenko, 2020; Deloitte, 2018).

Weyer et al. (2015) share this perspective. In their view, standardization is a necessary yet a significant challenge for extremely “modular, multi-vendor production systems.” A major challenge to having a successful modular factory structures is multi-vendor interoperability of automation technology. However, this can only be attained using coordinated standardization actions. In which case, standardization is crucial for guaranteeing interoperability between varied modules of Industry 4.0 production lines by enabling technology providers to engage in collaborative research and production systems, as well as present innovators with a chance to create and test how components from different manufacturers interact (Yang, 2014; Zhao & Liu, 2016). According to Weyer et al. (2015), designing and implementing such heterogeneous production lines through collaborative makes it possible to discover new gaps that could be addressed. Weyer et al. (2015) further observed that the significance of standardization in industry 4.0 becomes particularly relevant when it comes to the issue of electro-mechanical standards.

An effective collaboration of vendor-specific hardware and software alongside the capacity to successfully execute them and realize their full functionality depend on the standards that delineate the interface of different manufacturers. Essentially, the significance of manufacturing industry-standard systems in facilitating national transition to Industry 4.0 cannot be denied. Stock et al. (2018) explain that a full transition to industry 4.0 could only be possible with fundamental standards, which delineate the mechanical consistency among manufacturers’ modules. Examples include module dimensions along with the material flow such as those for innovative sluice systems and standardized conveyor belts.

The significance of communication standards also continued to be emphasised in current research. According to Stock et al. (2018), when it comes to communication interface, the requisite technological specifications will need to be defined to necessitate standardisations. Examples of these specifications include RFID data format, webserver technology, as well as OPC UA. For instance, the industrial communication protocol OPC UA permits manufacturing level application and retail level applications to be integrated vertically. This, therefore, suggests that all vendor-specific modules are not directly connected electrically or mechanically with respect to communication.

In related research, Stock et al. (2018) established that only those manufacturing enterprises that integrated a sustainable use of Industry 4.0 standards in their production system will attain a long term competitive edge. Stock et al. (2018) referred to an example of a collaborative project designed by the Fraunhofer Institute Austria, and the Vienna University of Technology, which evaluated production processes using a software-based value stream analysis to determine the sustainability of production systems. From the project, it was concluded that manufacturing enterprises that integrated a sustainable use of Industry 4.0 standards in their production system were most likely to attain a more sustainable competitive edge.

Critically, a number of studies concluded that routine and standardised production systems and activities would be easily automated and algorithmized by ICT (Standards Australia, 2017; Stock et al., 2018). In the case of Australia, the significance of manufacturing industry-standard systems in facilitating the transition to Industry 4.0 has been specifically highlighted by Standards Australia (2017) in its efforts to ensure that manufacturers in the country can connect and merge their production with ICTs to allow components and machines to autonomously manage production ways that are efficient and sustainable. According to Standards

Australia (2017) standardisation efforts should concentrate on defining the cooperation mechanisms and the information needed for exchange.

Already, countries like Germany have already set up standardisation initiatives targeted at enabling a national transition to industry 4.0. An example of such initiatives includes Germany's Plattform Industrie 4.0 (Standards Australia (2017)). Similar initiatives are being established in Australia under Standards Australia in collaboration with Australian Government, International Organization for Standardization (ISO), and International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC). Like the case of Germany, Standards Australia (2017) acknowledges that a successful transition to sustainable industry 4.0 would only be possible with having international standards fostering innovation, competitiveness, and growth. This demonstrates that a national transition to an innovation-led economy means will enable companies to leverage the opportunities promised by sustainable manufacturing if standardization is embraced to ensure coordinate collaboration internationally (Weyer et al, 2015).

2.3 Leveraging innovative capacity to ensure industry transition to industry 4.0

In his research, Sarkar (2013) took a strategic and holistic review on the manner in which eco-innovations alongside sustainable developmental and promotional efforts have stimulated the sustainable development of manufacturing industries as well as enhanced Green growth by creating verifiable eco-industrial models. Their study also describes a variety of entrepreneur and corporate initiatives that could be pursued to develop sustainable Eco-industrial business models for measuring the effects of eco-innovation projects. Sarkar (2013, p.72) defines eco-innovation as "the production, assimilation or exploitation of a product, production process, service or management or business method that is novel to the organization (developing or adopting it) and which results, throughout its life cycle, in a reduction of environmental risk, pollution and other negative impacts of resources use (including energy use) compared to relevant alternatives."

For manufacturers, the direct benefits of eco-innovation include operational advantages like cutting of costs to ensure greater resource productivity and improved logistics (Xu & Lin, 2015; Shao, 2017; Sailer, 2014). The indirect benefits include improve organizational reputation, improved relationship with customers, suppliers and regulatory authorities, as well as improved innovative capability overall. Such advantages should be compared against costs for the manufacturer (Sarkar, 2013). In his study, Sarkar (2013) found that majority of manufacturers surveyed had very minimal knowledge of the costs and benefits of their sustainable development activities. Building on this remark, Sarkar (2013) observed that eco-innovations need to be valued from a societal perspective, rather than a business standpoint.

Based on a social welfare perspective, eco-innovations are advantageous when they contribute to general welfare by virtue of societal wellbeing rather than merely economic growth (Xu & Lin, 2015; Shao, 2017; Sailer, 2014). An Eco-innovation is "any form of innovation resulting in or aiming at significant and verifiable advancement towards attaining sustainable development by minimizing environmental impacts, advancing organizations' resilience to environmental problems, as well as by ensuring that natural resources are use resourcefully. Sarkar (2013) also established that eco-innovation enables manufacturers by enabling them to leverage their innovative capacity to ensure transition to sustainable industry.

In their paper, Anadon et al. (2016) provided insights and recommended mechanisms for improving technological innovation with the view of enabling a faster transition to sustainable development. Their findings suggest that technological innovation processes do not adhere to sets sequences. Instead, they emerge

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from intricate adaptive systems that involved many actors and institutions that operate concurrently at the global or local scales. They also observed a tendency for barriers to continually emerge at virtually all stages of innovation, including at the point of inventing a technology to the point of selecting, producing, adapting, adopting, and retiring a technology (Schumpeter, 2002; Freeman, 1987; Khan & ManopichetwattanaV, 1989). They also found that manufacturers tended to learn from past attempts to marshal innovation with the view of attaining sustainable development and observed that this could significantly improve through structured cross-sectoral comparisons that put socio-technical aspects of innovation systems into perspective.

Anadon et al. (2016) also found that existing institutions, depending on their incentives, norms, and rules, fundamentally shape technological innovation, despite not having been aligned with the goals of sustainable development given that poorer, marginalized, and vulnerable populations tend to lack political and economic wherewithal to influence innovation systems to transition towards total sustainability. Yet, such institutions may still be transformed through research efforts, policymaking, and training. Against this backdrop, Anadon et al. (2016) concluded with three practice-based recommendations to facilitate the realization of the prospects of innovation for sustainable development. Additionally, manufacturers should undertake measures that can systematically take the interests of underserved populations into considerations. Lastly, there is a need to reform institutions to enable them to re-orientate innovation systems toward sustainable development and make sure that all stages and scales of innovation are taken into consideration at the start (Xu & Lin, 2015; Shao, 2017). Across the research, it has also been established that to make innovation to work for sustainable development as well as for populations that lack power, there is a need to conceptualize the innovation process and to identify barriers to innovation.

2.4 Effects of digital infrastructure on rural manufacturing sector's transition to industry 4.0

In their study, Randall et al. (2020) observed that digital divide was a key barrier to national transition to sustainable industry, innovations, and infrastructure, particularly in rural areas. Besides the infrastructure shortcomings, rural areas also undergo barriers as far as the skills and knowledge needed to unlock digitalisation opportunities is concerned. Digital competence is mostly concentrated in major urban areas than rural areas. In their baseline survey, Randall et al. (2020) examine the character of digital transformation in rural and remote regions and made recommendations on how digital infrastructure can be leveraged in the rural manufacturing sector to facilitate national transition to sustainable industry, innovations, and infrastructure in Nordic countries and in Latvia. Their findings proved to be relevant for review, particularly as it provides a context for the digitalisation of small scale manufacturers in rural areas.

An important finding from their research is that digitalisation has a significant potential to allow rural areas to join in the national transition to sustainable industry. This is because it enables individuals to triumph over the challenges linked to geographical distances, making sure that equal opportunities are accessible to all (Lundvall 1992; Charles & Zabala-Iturriagoitia, 2012; Zhang 2012. In the manufacturing sector, it is concerned with new ways of organising work, such as by enabling the conception and adoption of new business models. Collectively, such developments can enable manufacturers to address many challenges that rural areas have to contend with such as skills shortages (Randall et al. 2020).

In a related study, Prakash (2018) also acknowledged the significance of spreading infrastructure development in rural areas to encourage sustainable industrialisation in Africa. The research outlined that Africa experiences development gaps at both the geographical and industrial levels. Geographical

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development gaps refer to disparities in income levels and stages of development among African countries. On the other hand industrial development gaps consist of disparities in stages of productivity between local and multinational firms (Hou et al, 2019; Zheng & Zhong, 2010). An important finding by Prakash (2018) is that by investing in digital infrastructure, rural manufacturing sectors could also be allowed to participate in national transition to sustainable industry, innovations, and infrastructure by closing the geographical and industrial gaps in their regions of operation (Prakash, 2018). Prakash (2018) also observed that as Africa continues to catch up with growth trends in various fields, investment plans will need to concentrate on creating infrastructure, institutions, and capacities in the rural areas to facilitate a transition to sustainable industry, innovations, and infrastructure. Prakash's (2018) review of the development lessons from Europe suggested a trend whereby growth and development could only become sustainable if sufficiently understood by their vast populations. In this regard, Prakash (2018) recommended a need for manufacturing firms in rural areas to focus on improving livelihoods of their communities and enable growth that is sustainable and scalable.

2.5 Mechanisms for improving industrial structure to enable realization of SDG9

According to IISD (2017), sustainable Development Goal 9 (SDG 9) is anchored in industry, infrastructure, and innovation. Essentially, any strategy targeted at improving industrial structure to enable realization of Goal 9 of the SDG should focus on these three pillars. In any case, IISD (2017) observed that the three pillars are all intended to achieve sustainable socially inclusive and environmentally inclusive economic development. It is on the strength of this argument that IISD (2017) argued that to realize SDG 9, manufacturing firms should aim to overcome resource constraints, build and strengthen their innovative capacities, and explore innovative means for resolution of underlying development challenges. This appears to be a workable strategy for building resilient infrastructure, promoting sustainable industrialization and fostering innovation (Li et al., 2016; Hou et al, 2019; Zheng & Zhong, 2010).

It their thematic review, IISD (2017) also described challenges to attaining SDG as directly linked to political and financial will. Their review gave emphasis to the idea that efforts to prevail over such barriers are ongoing but would involve major political and financing will. A major challenge is linked to the necessity for improving Internet access by manufacturing enterprises in developing countries. Their review further drew attention to the fact that oftentimes, access is not synonymous to use due to issues linked to low ICT literacy rates, affordability, and scarcity of local content. Accordingly, there is a need to strengthen ICT skills of manufacturing enterprises, develop pertinent Internet content, strengthen regulatory frameworks, and promote trust as these would make sure that improved access translates to improved use (UNCTAD, 2021).

An additional challenge is linked to insufficient transport, which contributes to higher costs of trading, and reduced competitiveness of exports. At the same time, meagre access to infrastructure, specifically for transportation, energy, and electricity, encumbers development, value addition, and diversification in agro-industry, specifically in rural areas (IISD, 2017). Another study by Kumar et al. (2016) also emphasised a need for policies that facilitate infrastructural development. Kumar et al. (2016) observed that countries in South Asia have wide infrastructure gaps in comparison to other countries in Asia and the Pacific, which hinders their attempt to realize SDG9.

Agarwal et al. (2017) also explains that funding the implementation of SDG 9 would call for considerable investments in infrastructure and innovation. Although much advancement has been made, there is still a need

for more financing and investments particularly in rural areas to help attain SDG 9 goals. IISD (2017) observed that this is definitely the problem in rural areas where close to 1.1 billion people are not connected to the electricity grid. IISD (2017) also emphasised a need for the development of partnership, tools, and programs among manufacturing enterprises to facilitate advancement on SDG9. The goals of such partnerships should be aligned with helping in the realization of national industrialization priorities. Agarwal et al. (2017) also argues that for manufacturing enterprises to deliver on the SDGs, they need to widen and intensify their engagement and being emphasising elemental alignment of their core business practices with sustainable development. Their review of the research on SDG9 indicated a readiness for manufacturers apply a 'cost-benefit' approach to the management of community relations. Accordingly, an underlying challenge for most manufacturers, as Agarwal et al. (2017) observed, is how they can pursue a transition from applying relatively narrow business case approach to lining up their core activities with the more extensive interests and values of their societies. On the strength of this argument, Agarwal et al. (2017) identified three pathways for creating the conditions that manufacturers may pursue to attain the SDG9 goals.

These include increasing ambitions surrounding the degree of change required by manufacturers to attain the SDGs. This is particularly the case for businesses and SDG community that need to promote a new narrative of what constitutes consequential engagement in the SDG, including by having opinion leaders who demonstrate a strong support for disruptive innovators and underscoring the viability of integrating sustainable business strategies (Agarwal et al., 2017). They also highlighted a need to underscore external conditions for highly ambitious business engagements with sustainable industry, innovations, and infrastructure. One of these conditions includes forming partnerships among civil society, investors, and governments. This is in agreement with IISD's (2017) suggestion of a need for the development of partnership, tools, and programs among manufacturing enterprises to facilitate advancement on SDG9 (Yang, 2014; Zhao & Liu, 2016). According to Agarwal et al. (2017), such a partnership would enable key stakeholders to work together to direct greater alignment among the strategies of enterprises and sustainable development. In effect, it will make it possible for the government to make binding rules and set agendas, that reward more significant SDG engagement among manufacturing enterprises, and exposes irresponsible behaviours in the society through the civil society. Agarwal et al. (2017) also emphasised the need to extend the base of relevant key stakeholders and issues. This is, according to Agarwal et al. (2017), because vulnerable groups like individuals that live in poverty that are affected by business operations characteristically lack the authority to shape manufacturing enterprises' business case calculations. Under such scenarios, societal considerations may not be included in such calculations.

2. Theoretical Framework

This research used the Institutional Theory, as the underlying theoretical framework. Areas of how institutions and government are encouraging the companies to participate in reaching national objectives are main topics to discuss. Topics such as degree of autonomy that enterprises have towards conducting their own individual practices will also be discussed to evaluate the highest motivators for reaching the sustainability and discussed objectives in the SDG 9. Research methods will be based on qualitative analysis of already collected data by other researchers (Baumol & Litan, 2008). As much of the information is based on the statistical data from countries themselves, explanatory research approach allows discussing and interpreting

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data. In this way, comparison and discussions sections were conducted in accordance with written literature and research done by other researchers.

To understand the role of Chinese manufacturing enterprises in the national transition towards sustainable industry, innovations, and infrastructure, the institutional theory had to be employed as an overarching theoretical framework (Huq & Stevenson, 2020). The theory suggests a framework for exploring how organizations increasingly act in response to a mixture of pressures from actors in their industry or field of operation by converging on a combination of harmonized business practices that eventually transform into the legitimate or conventional business practice (Grewal and Dharwadkar 2002)

Institutional theory hypothesises that enterprises adopt organizational practices primarily as a result of three forms of pressure (Grewal and Dharwadkar 2002): coercive pressures, mimetic pressures, and normative pressures. Coercive pressures are those wielded by powerful organizations in a network. Normative pressures are exerted by professionalization before being passed through professional networks and formal education. Lastly, mimetic pressures happen when organizations, as a result of uncertainty, copy the practices of successful competitors (Lai et al., 2016; Scott, 2018). In the context of the manufacturing sector, a number of institutional actors potentially exert pressures that influence the practices that should be legitimated (Scott 2008).

The institutional theory offers a theoretical framework for identifying and examining influences that encourage the legitimacy and existence of organizational practices, including factors like regulations, social environment and cultural environment, and economic incentives, while simultaneously appreciating the significance of resources (Glover et al. 2013). The term legitimacy consists of stakeholder's acceptability of and adoption of scarce resources. In effect, institutional theory's fundamental concern is how organizations can SECURE strong legitimacy and positions by way of adhering to regulatory systems, such as policies, laws or governmental agencies. The theory further reasons that economic, social and political pressures shape organization's strategies and decision-making in the attempt to adopt legitimize certain practices with focus on stakeholders' interests (Glover et al. 2013). It is characterized by:

- Process by which an institution attains a stable and durable state or property
- An organization is a player, while institutions are the rules of the game
- Functionalism and limited rationality: unintended consequences of action in organizations
- External environments: boundary between authority in the organization and legitimacy bestowed
- Attenuated consciousness: degree to which actors are conscious of institutional conditions
- Symbolic life of organizations: institutionalism emphasizes the symbolic role of formal organizational structures in contrast to informal interactions and specific local or technical interests

3. Method

4.1 Research approach and strategy

Research method was based on qualitative analysis of already collected data by other researchers. As much of the information is based on the statistical data from countries themselves, explanatory research approach made it possible to discuss and interpret the collected data. This way, comparison and discussions sections can

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be conducted in accordance with written literature and research done by other researchers. There are little descriptive articles found covering the research questions. Majority of the literature available is related to reports, where statistical data obtain from observations and national statistical bureaus is introduced. With the available data, innovative companies' role in interconnectivity with public structures is devaluated. China's disparities in geography, sociology, economy, and development cannot be covered with the current literature or analysis that considers the whole country as one unit.

As regards the research strategy, a decision was made to use a case study research to explore China's manufacturing sector as the research setting. In using a case study research strategy, emphasis was placed on exploring how China can Chinese manufacturers develop the unit labour output through science and technology in order to facilitate national transition towards sustainable industry, innovations and infrastructure, and the how the manufacturing industry can leverage standard systems of industrialization to successfully transition to Industry 4.0. Focus was also placed on exploring the country's innovative capacity and how it could be leveraged to ensure a smooth and speedy transition to sustainable industry, innovations, and infrastructure, how the digital infrastructure can be leveraged in the rural manufacturing sector to facilitate national transition to sustainable industry, innovations, and infrastructure, as well as the strategies recommended for improving the country's industrial structure to enable realization of Goal 9 of the SDG.

Technically, an underlying principle for a case study research is to facilitate knowledge construction of a complexity of sectoral issues. In the case of this study, sectoral case study research involved undertaking a comprehensive contextual analysis of Chinese manufacturing companies' role in the national transition towards sustainable industry, innovations, and infrastructure. A case study approach made it possible to consult different sources of evidence of how the sector has performed relative to industry 4.0, such as media content, policy documents, research papers, and working papers.

Data for the sectoral research was collected using document analysis. Document analysis is a type of qualitative research with focus on interpretation of documents to assign meanings around a topic under review (Bowen, 2009). The process integrates coding of data into themes. Focus was placed on three types of documents: personal documents, public records, and physical evidence. Public records targeted and drawn into the research include fragmentary records of manufacturers' activities, such as policy manuals, research journals, annual reports, market and industry reports, and strategic plans. Personal documents consisted of first-personal accounts of manufacturing experiences, such as incident reports, newspapers, and blogs. Lastly, physical evidence consisted of artefacts like manufacturers' handbooks, and agendas.

4.2 Research Rationale

Document analysis was selected for this research, as it is a vital research tool in its own right. The rationale for selecting document analysis was because it was expected to review a range of data to attain convergence (Bowen, 2009). A number of reasons underpinned the decision to use document analysis. First, document analysis was expected to provide a high level of efficiency and effectiveness in data collection, given that documents used were expected to be convenient and practical resources. Essentially, given the wide scope of the research and the limited budget and timeline for the research, a decision was made to use readily accessible documents as they are readily accessible and come in a range of forms. This makes documents to be highly reliable and accessible data sources. Acquisition and analysis of documents were found convenience, owing to their cost efficiency and time efficiency, in comparison to undertaking individual experiments and

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research (Bowen, 2009). Additionally, documents were selected as they are intrinsically nonreactive or stable. This means that they can be reread and reviewed severally yet still remain unaffected by the research process and influence. Another reason for using document analysis in this research was to facilitate drawing of data from a broad diversity of sectoral documents, which were then used to corroborate data collected from research journals and books.

An additional underlying reason for selecting document analysis is because it was expected to offer background information and facilitate extensive data coverage, and in the process be supportive in contextualization of the research on the Chinese manufacturing companies' role in the national transition towards sustainable industry, innovations, and infrastructure within its field. Documents also consisted of data that could not be observed conveniently, such as how the digital infrastructure can be leveraged in the rural manufacturing sector to facilitate national transition to sustainable industry, innovations, and infrastructure, and the strategies that should be recommended for improving the country's industrial structure to enable realization of Goal 9 of the SDG.

The review of the documents was based on dimensions of the "Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses" (PRISMA) guidelines (Tranfield et al., 2003). Collection of secondary data was based on reviewing pertinent materials, such as theses, articles, working papers, conference presentations, and other relevant documents accessed on the internet (Mensah, Casadevall, 2019). Document identification was based on an integration of searches, whereby keywords linked to Chinese manufacturing companies' role in the national transition towards sustainable industry, innovations, and infrastructure. As any relevant document was targeted for review, it was determined that there is no need to impose date restrictions on the search. In effect, precedence was given to the weight of the documents with respect to their significant contributions to current discourses on the drive for national transition towards SDG9 in China. At any rate, efforts were made to capture recently published documents as this was expected to help reveal the currency and growing bearing of the topic to China's sectoral research. For this reason, documents found to be unrelated to sustainability and development in the manufacturing sector could be excluded. To avert risks of missing likely relevant documents, reference lists of the selected ones were skimmed for topics that relate to materials under study. Accordingly, the title and abstracts of documents could be examined prior to including them in the research (Mensah, Casadevall, 2019).

Selected documents that met the pre-defined inclusion criteria - such as by being authoritative, relevant, and current - were given priority. For instance, relevance concerned the contribution of the materials to ongoing discourses on Chinese manufacturing companies' role in the national transition towards sustainable industry, innovations, and infrastructure. Authority referred to whether the documents selected were reliable based on their publisher - such as whether they are peer reviewed or originate from concerned stakeholders in the manufacturing industry. Currency concerned whether the documents were recently published and are strictly concerned about SDG9 discourses. Overall, around 150 relevant documents were identified. However, after they were screened for eligibility processes, the number of articles that met the criteria was (Mensah, Casadevall, 2019).

In the process of analysis, full texts could be systematically to extract relevant data, which were then analysed using qualitative content analysis - particularly thematic analysis techniques. In which case, data from the documents were coded or summated under themes. For this reason, pertinent information could be summated repeatedly, based on keywords. The sequence of summarizations, which had to be manually

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performed, was expected to bring out basic results with respect to the point of view of each input data as well as to eliminate any discrepancy and irrelevance of data. The rationale for doing away with certain dimensions of each summary result was observed in the preparation of the summary so as to avoid forgetting the reasons why they were excluded. Afterwards, data gathered by means of summations were then synthesised, prior to being interwoven and paraphrased to ensure concision, condensation, and coherence. The resulting content consisted of a highly concise and refined summation of the pertinent documents that demonstrated how Chinese manufacturers developed the unit labour output to facilitate national transition towards sustainable industry, innovations and infrastructure, how the manufacturing industry standard systems could be leveraged to facilitate the transition to Industry 4.0, how China's innovative capacity could be leveraged to ensure a smooth and speedy transition, and how the digital infrastructure can be leveraged in the rural manufacturing sector to facilitate national transition to sustainable industry, innovations, and infrastructure. Also critical to this study were the strategies that Chinese manufacturing enterprises should pursue to improve the country's industrial structure to enable realization of SDG9. Industry, Innovations and Infrastructure is one of the Sustainable Development Goals by United Nations. China as one of the most important contributors to the world development is also highly affected by the usage of natural resources and pollution. Currently, 27.5% of people are working in industrial companies. With increasing average age of the society members, new ways of how to sustain growth will have to be discovered- one of them is the deployment of IT systems which would modernize the manufacturing technologies to remove the necessity of employees doing physical labour

Newest trends show the shift from electronics production to high tech equipment manufacturing in developed and emerging countries. With higher labor costs in China than in other South East Asian countries, manufacturing companies are looking for ways how to increase production efficiency or new products to offer to the market in order to sustain attractiveness. In Mainland China similarly to abroad, servitization is another increasing importance aspect how to sustain client base. Companies are shifting from manufacturing simple products to offering solutions to the customers. SDG 9 is promoting sustainable, ecologically produced goods are offering additional value to the issues related pollution, overconsumption of material and poor recycling.

Main research areas are related to manufacturing companies who are adapting production software systems, robotics, automated technologies which can assist companies in better planning and manufacturing the goods. These technologies can be related to better management of time, employee distribution, material usage, better logistics, and quality control. Usually, issues related to product lifetime can motivate the consumers to throw out the items much earlier than otherwise the possible service period. Therefore, research related to the areas of sustainability, technologies, manufacturing practices, speed of implementation and goods production will be part of the research project.

4.3 Research Process

Prior to the actual process of document review, there was a need to go through an exhaustive planning process to guarantee consistent results. Correspondingly, an 8-step planning process was pursued, as proposed by O'Leary (2014). The first process includes creating a list of texts to explore, which mainly included written texts on Chinese manufacturers. The process of considering how texts on manufacturers in China would be accessed followed this. The third process entailed acknowledging and addressing biases, followed by developing proper skills for research. Focus had also to be placed on considering strategies for guaranteeing credibility of texts collected, and knowledge of the data to target for the research. Consideration was then

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given to ethical concerns, including acknowledging the data sources. In the last stage, consideration was given to a back-up plan for data collection to ensure that sources targeted yet had no reliable data would be replaced by other data sources with relatively credible data.

Overall, a huge plethora of texts were used in this research, even as written texts formed the backdrop of the research. Two key issues were considered in the commencement document analysis. This included giving a consideration to concerns over bias. Therefore, consideration was given to the issue of subjectivity as well as personal biases in the interpretation of documents analysed. According to Bowen (2009), a researcher should focus on evaluating the document's original intent and whether the author was a firsthand witness or not. Consideration was also given to the establishing whether the document under review was anonymous, edited, original, or solicited. The second issue included latent content of documents under review, such as fact, agenda, opinions, or tone. Accordingly, the documents were evaluated for their completeness, or comprehensiveness of their data. Also of paramount importance when evaluating documents is not to consider the data as "necessarily precise, accurate, or complete recordings of events that have occurred" (Bowen, 2009, p. 33). These issues are summed up in another eight-step process offered by O'Leary (2014).

In the process of data analysis, it was found necessary to employ the READ approach. It consists of a systematic process of gathering documents and obtaining information from the documents in the context of investigating the role of perfecting standard systems of industrialization in the attempt to transition to Industry 4.0, and examining how China's innovative capacity can be leveraged to ensure a smooth and speedy transition to sustainable industry, innovations, and infrastructure. The steps pursued in data analysis included (a) readying materials, (b) extracting data, (a) analysing data and (4) distilling findings (Dalglish, et al., 2020).

In readying the materials, focus was placed on setting parameters regarding the nature and quantity of documents planned for analysis, dependent on the research objectives. Data extraction involved extracting data and coding data into emerging themes. The data analysis and data collection process were iterative and were typified by emergent design. This means that developing findings repetitively informed whether as well as the manner in which to acquire and interpret data. This implies that in the data extraction phase, focus was placed on data analysis and formation of initial theories. Lastly, the process of distilling findings entailed refining the findings and illustrating them with graphics (Dalglish, et al., 2020).

Before collecting data, a qualitative research method was selected over a quantitative research as this research had to focus on interpreting how China should focus on developing the unit labor output of China through science and technology in order to take advantage of industrial 4.0, so as to transition towards sustainable industry, innovations, and infrastructure. Being an explanatory study, there were enough grounds to use a qualitative research approach to explain the research phenomenon, as it has not been exhaustively and conclusively explored and explained (Dalglish, et al., 2020).

In effect, from the review of the literature, it was observed that a number of studies have concluded that in spite of recent manufacturing practices that have underscored that China's relatively weak innovative capacity and insufficiency of core talents, compared to developed countries like China, is another major challenge to a speedy transition to sustainable industry, innovations and infrastructure, under the broad spectrum of Industry 4.0. There was a feeling across a body of research literature review that there is a need for explanatory research that could explain how environmental pollution has challenged successful transition to a sustainable

industry and recommends strategies for improving the country's industrial structure to enable it to meet Goal 9 of the SDG. These provided broad justification for using an explanatory research.

4. Data Analysis

The analysis centres chiefly on manufacturing sub-sectors, such as ICT, household appliances, toys, footwear and textile and clothing. A majority of the documents reviewed seemed to focus on these sub-sectors, particularly in the area of Chinese manufacturers' labour output and their drive to meet sustainable development. This provided a strong basis for investigating the potential of manufacturing relocation in sectors where variations in employments have tended to be dynamic in recent years, hence providing sufficient data for investigating Chinese manufacturers' labour output to meet sustainable development. The data is based on data drawn from numerous official sources, primarily collated from National Bureau of Statistics China (NBSC). On the other hand, the statistics for wages and jobs in the manufacturing sub-sectors are drawn from a variety of statistical yearbooks, such as Industry Economic Statistic Yearbook (IESY) (2006–2020). From thematic analysis, a number of themes emerge that are directly linked to the research objectives. Hence, measures are ensured to make sure that themes selected in this review are coincided with the research objectives.

Theme 1: Role of Chinese manufacturers' labour output in ensuring sustainable development

It emerges from content analysis that China's labour market reforms are largely tied to the comprehensive, third-plenum reform blueprint of 2013, which has, however, seemed to have focused on the economic, social, and environmental benefits from the sector's output. This leads to the assumption that China's manufacturing sector is moving towards a more sustainable and inclusive growth. A report by the People's Congress (2015) demonstrates that economic reform efforts in the country are also shifting towards a 'New Normal,' whereby the manufacturing market's labour sector has to be restructured to support long-term sustainable growth (Cho et al., 2017; Liu 2014). Yet, this also points to a need for the sector to focus on bridging continually emerging skills gaps, as the traditional economic drivers such as the middle class, has to be slowly but surely replaced by newer drivers, consisting of upper-middle-class workers along with the service sector.

What also seems to be clear is that the New Normal transformation in China is creating newer types of challenges, such as skills gaps to transition to Industry 4.0. There are also indications that China's manufacturing enterprises have built on the low wage advantage, even as the country is experiencing speedy development that has been instrumental in achieving extraordinary GDP growth. It is on the premise that the country surpassed the United States in 2011 as the largest manufactured goods producer in the world. Yet, because of current emphasis on Chinese manufacturers' labour output to meet sustainable development, there continues to be indications across the manufacturing sector's analysis on the need for enterprises to pursue mechanisms for surviving because of the decelerating economic growth, an increase in factor costs, and growing labour shortages (Shao, 2017; Sailer, 2014; Yang, 2014). Indeed, in spite of the drive for sustainability, it has become more and trickier for the manufacturing sector to maintain comparative advantages as it is also increasingly become sensitive to costs of labour (Li et al., 2020). It could be argued

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from this perspective that rising wages and other factor costs are dampening the sector's competitiveness, which is changing the perception that the country is a low-cost centre for labour-intensive products.

Essentially, these imply that China requires new growth sources after the old growth model propelled by investment began running out of steam. In 2021, the Chinese government published its plans in the draft of its 14th five-year plan for 2021-25, which sets out the pathway for attaining economic and labour productivity growth in the period 2021-2025. A review of the plan indicates the country's acknowledgement of the necessity to close skills gaps in order to improve labour output by improving education and rural education. However, a major question remains whether focus should be placed on state-owned enterprises or the private sector (Li et al., 2020).

These also indicate a need for China to locate new sources of growth that can trigger increased labour output that meets sustainable development. At any rate, current data by National Bureau of Statistics indicates that the growth of labour productivity, as determined by gross domestic product (GDP) per individual workers has been relatively high, consistent with GDP growth in the period 2016-2021, mainly because of total economic growth rate of 2.3% (Leng & Lee, 2021).

China's overall labour output challenge is high owing to an extensive measure of how efficiently the country manufacturing sector utilizes labour and capital, which are essentially total factor productivity (TFP). Concerns that the labour force could gradually shrink and deleverage could mean a more sluggish investment and capital accumulation, which could in turn cause a failed TFP growth. Such estimates correspond with analysis published by the World Bank in 2019, which stated that the TFP growth rate had decreased by around 1.55% in the period 2008-2017. In spite of the fact that a declining working population in the manufacturing sector, as evident from a fall by nearly 7 million in the period 2021-2025, could contribute to a decline in productivity or labour output, this may not actually be the case as more focus is placed on innovation. Elsewhere, studies have showed that even when the workforce is relatively small yet skilled, innovative, and highly educated, the sector could still experience improved labour output (Li & Liu, 2011; Xu & Lin, 2015; Shao, 2017; Sailer, 2014).

Pursuing the path of innovation and education, is therefore, critical for ensuring that Chinese manufacturers' labour output meets sustainable development. Already, the government appreciates the value of investing in education and innovation to meet sustainability goals. This could be explained by the government's current plans to increase the average number of years that students can spend in school from 10.8 in 2021 to 11.3 in 2025. There are indications in economic literature that increased high school educational attainment, specifically in rural China, could be instrumental in enabling the manufacturing sector to meet sustainability goals (Foreman-Peck, 2013; Cho et al., 2017; Liu 2014). The issue of educational attainment is a major concern in China, in comparison to developed nations like the United States. In 2016, for instance, less than 50% of students in the rural areas of China could graduate from high school, in comparison to close to 90% in the United State (Leng & Lee, 2021). The trend in China can be credited to the idea that many rural children opt to drop from school and to follow in the footsteps of their parents to locate manual labour in cities.

China has made significant advancement in the last two decades with respect to education. This includes putting up measures to implement compulsory schooling for children in the age group 6-15 years old, and facilitating the attainment of universal primary enrolment and gender equality in education. Statistics by DEG (2016) indicate that nearly 74 percent of Chinese students attend upper secondary school, although this is in

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major cities. Additionally, 43 percent of those who attend upper secondary school get to attend a vocational institution. In spite of such advancements, the country still needs to invest more in education to fill the manufacturing sector's current skills gaps and to meet industry 4.0 goals (DEG, 2016).

The United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO) has highlighted the significance of pursuing skills development as major driver of Industry 4.0. According to UNIDO (2017), manufacturing enterprises should pursue a pro-active skills transformation by shaping the young generation to be "robotic natives" in order to meet the skills requirements for industry 4.0. Attempts to invest more in skill development among manufacturing enterprises in the sector indicate a finding that is adequately supported in research, which elaborates how inclusive and sustainable industrial development (ISID) can only be met by players in the manufacturing sector who transform their workforce into digital natives who can coexist and collaborate with intelligent machines (Beier et al., 2018; Gabriel and Pessl, 2016).

A case study review of manufacturing firms in the industry demonstrates a growing trend towards skill development, with growing focus on sustainable development. For instance, a case of Hape Holding AG (a Chinese company that manufactures toys that is situated in Beilun) in East China shows greater focus towards skill development in the use of renewable materials like bamboo and wood (DEG, 2016). Skill development has ensured the production of innovative and high-quality toys that guarantee high quality to customers. In the shift towards Industry 4.0, the company's major challenges included tackling its skills gaps and as a result came up with an out-and-out three-year vocational-training program for wood-workers, which guaranteed the supply of sufficiently trained workers. When it comes to skills development along the company's value chain, Hape trained wood and bamboo suppliers on how to improve the quality of their supplies. In this way, Hape has benefitted from a highly innovative and better-educated workforce and quality supplies that have boosted the quality of its output (DEG, 2016).

From the case of Hape, it becomes clear that for manufacturing enterprises to address similar skills gaps with focus on helping to transition the country to Industry 4.0, they should focus on systematic evaluation and development of internal talents, developing a vocational training program with focusing on meeting sustainability needs, and fostering intra-firm knowledge circulation. Hape's case scenario also indicates that when manufacturing enterprises invest in skills development of their workforce, as well as along the value chain, it becomes more possible to bridge local skills gaps and to attain the ideals of Industry 4.0. Besides investment in skilled workforce, there is an emerging trend for Chinese manufacturing enterprises to adopt unmanned factories by investing in industrial robots. A report by the Global Skills Summit (2016) also shows that even as China is a low-cost country, manufacturing enterprises in the country still operate in the age of Industry 2.0. This means that it is still generally labor intensive, although it is in the process of executing Industry 3.0 technologies.

With respect to the adoption of advanced technology, the country has been slow, in spite of making progress in its attempt to bridge the gap towards attaining industry 4.0. As indicated by a market research by Fraunhofer IOA, the country registered nearly 2,500 patents for Industry 4.0-enabling technology in 2016. In 2014, the country launched "36 multipurpose robots per 10,000 employees in the manufacturing industry vis-à-vis an average world robot density of 66" (Global Skills Summit, 2016). It has gradually closed the gap, as evident from steps in procuring nearly 57,000 robots at the end of that year. Such measures pursued by the government and manufacturing enterprises clearly indicated that the country has been proactive in advancing its Industry 3.0 to Industry 4.0. The Chinese government has spearheaded the Industry 4.0 through

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policymaking to ensure that Chinese manufacturers substantially improve the quality of manufacturing and manufacturing output by integrating industrialization and digitalization (Müller & Voig, 2018).

Measures to introduce industrial robots indicate a growing enthusiasm by the sector to meet Industry 4.0 goals, and improved quality of output. A review of current industry trends indicate that manufacturing enterprises are taking to unmanned factories (Müller & Voig, 2018). For instance, a mobile phone manufacturing firm known as Changying Precision Technology Company has been at the forefront of robotization by going completely automated at its manufacturing plants in Dongguan. The factory currently utilizes robotic arms for production of smartphone components. Global Skills Summit (2016) identified Changying Precision's production lines as the first of a kind in China to be operated using computer-controlled robots. Yet, the practice of adopting industrial robots has been controversial (DEG, 2016). While they have improved the quality and quantity of output per production line, they have had adverse impacts on the country's workforce. Global Skills Summit (2016) observed a trend whereby the number of employees at Changying Precision Technology's factory in Dongguan declined to 60 from 650, even as the rate of defects reduced significantly to 5% from 25% after the introduction of industrial robots. Evidence of robotization to meet Industry 4.0 goals can also be explained from the context of Ningbo Techmation, a company that manufactures plastic equipment. In 2014, the company launched a robot manufacturing plant called E-Deodar, and has substantially invested in R&D to help make cheaper robots (DEG, 2016).

Attempts to invest more in skill development among manufacturing enterprises in the sector point towards a finding that is adequately supported in research, which elaborates how inclusive and sustainable industrial development (ISID) can only be met by players in the manufacturing sector who transform their workforce into digital natives who can coexist and collaborate with intelligent machines (Beier et al., 2018; Gabriel and Pessl, 2016). It is on this basis that some reports by the World Bank (2020) indicated that in the attempt to meet industry 4.0 goals, China is making measures to transition from a low-cost and labour-intensive production to modern manufacturing industry. This is the case with Guangdong Province, which has earned a global reputation for being the "world's factory," have been a traditional large-scale producer of textiles, shoes and toys. Currently, however, Guangdong Province is transitioning from a low-cost and labour-intensive industry to one that is highly robotized and service-oriented. However, challenges associated with skills gaps indicate that more focus will need to be placed on investment in education and skills development. Indeed, as observed by the World Bank (2020), transitioning to Industry 4.0 for a country like China requires greater investment in a high-skilled industrial workforce and more technical schools. Indeed, in alignment with such expectation, Guangdong Province has invested in 156 technical schools with a carrying capacity of 558,000 students.

Across the research, it is strongly advocated that when it comes to transition to Industry 4.0, focus should be placed on the quality of labour productivity, without which manufacturing enterprises are likely to be stuck by a workforce that cannot work side by side with advanced technologies. García-Muiña et al. (2020) reasons that manufacturers' unit labour outputs may only enable a national transition towards industry 4.0 once there is sufficient investment in a human capital with advanced technological knowhow. Accordingly, to guarantee this, manufacturing enterprises should be made to realize the implications of industry 4.0 technologies on improving production processes in manners that are highly efficient and capable of facilitating sustainable development. In spite of this, an underlying concern for China's manufacturing enterprises remains accessing

highly skilled workforce to meet the technological knowledge gaps needed for industry 4.0 (Machado et al, 2019).

An industry survey by McKinsey Institute (2021) confirms that although China has an education system that supports the industrial economy, skills gaps would make it difficult for the country to transition fast to Industry 4.0 because of concerns related to quality output. According to McKinsey Institute (2021), the country still needs to overcome the challenge to delivering requisite skills for a post-industrial economy (Woetzel et al., 2021). The report also recommended a need for China to also instil a “new national ethos of lifelong learning.” Yet, this is not unique to China. Across the globe, work is evolving with focus on ensuring digitization and keeping up with the spread of robotization in the manufacturing sector. For this reason, McKinsey Institute (2021) highlighted that the global workforce needs to advance and refresh their skills to meet evolving occupations (Woetzel et al., 2021).

Beier et al. (2018) attempted to explain the reason for this emphasis on skills development. In their view, manufacturers’ labour output can also be leveraged to meet sustainable development once the workforce’s innovative capacity and computer literacy is improved, with focus on ensuring sustainable development. Beier et al. (2018) further elaborated that a sustainable transition process to industry 4.0 should substantially depend on effective operational introduction of sustainability practices. Yet, care should be taken to ensure that transitional process to industry 4.0 does not overlook the strategic evolution of manufacturing enterprises with regard to leveraging a highly technological advanced labour to facilitate value creation. García-Muiña et al. (2020) discusses that this is the trend that the United States pursued. From a study of manufacturing enterprises in the US, García-Muiña et al. (2020) explained how the process of implementing sustainability is intrinsically complex and that it requires a medium-long-term strategic vision, effective communication between business units and the executive management, as well as the level of employee competence and quality of their productivity.

In light of these findings, a number of recommendations can be made. According to Global Skills Summit (2016), focus should first be on the assessment of skill demand for future Industry 4.0. To ensure this, a governance body should be established in collaboration with manufacturing enterprises and representations from Industry 4.0 end users to assess the current state of skills sufficiency and projected skills gaps. This will ensure that skills development both in the education sector and among manufacturing enterprises is aligned with future skill requirements. There is also a need to improve the course content of training in line with the projected skills gaps (Foreman-Peck, 2013; Cho et al., 2017; Liu 2014). The Global Skills Summit (2016) observes that this is crucial since the gap between skill sets on demand and skill sets supplied into the manufacturing sector will keep rising with a continued transition to Industry 4.0. At the same time, measures should be taken to include Industry 4.0 solution providers in developing course content of training to ensure that their inputs on technologies are put into consideration. An additional significant aspect of skill development is efficient provision of skill training to young people in China. As recommended in a report by Global Skills Summit (2016), focus should be placed in expanding the number of skill development colleges, such as vocational training schools to encourage and add to reach of vocational education.

Theme 2: Effects of industry-standard systems on transition to Industry 4.0

A review of documentary evidence on China's industry standards indicates conscious measures to develop industry-standard systems that can facilitate the country's transition to Industry 4.0. For instance, on January 15, 2021 China's Ministry of Industry and Information Technology ("MIIT") made public the Guidelines for Building Basic Security Standard System for the Internet of Things. The government expects to establish not less than 30 industry standards by 2025 (Baruzzi, 2021). The standards are targeted at improving the security level of IoT cross-industry application.

Standardisation is considered to be essential for manufacturing enterprises considering the variable influences of IoT on manufacturing, the rapidly increasing number of connected devices used in the sector. At the same time, data shared via connected devices will need to be effectively processed, managed, transferred, and stored using standardised systems. Baruzzi (2021) used this perspective to argue that it is increasingly becoming critical for uniform standards to be established to allow rapidly advancing technologies applied in manufacturing to be manufactured in ways that they could be used to manufacture scalable products. Essentially, scalable products can be designed, produced, and used globally.

Already, the government has come up with China Standard Plan 2035, which are intended for the technology innovation sector. According to Baruzzi (2021), the need to provide standards in the innovation technology sector is underscored in the China Standards Plan 2035, which is expected to drive the Chinese government and guide manufacturing enterprises to set global standards for Industry 4.0 technologies, like artificial intelligence Internet of Things, and 5G internet. Critically, the idea of setting up industry standards for technology innovation has intrinsic value, in terms of enabling interoperability among Industry 4.0 technological innovations and their universal usability. Yet, the idea of standardisation appears to be proving to be a challenge for China, particularly as representatives from Western countries dominate international panels (Ziegler, 2016). This implies that China should make efforts to change the status quo to make sure that designing of standards are aligned with the technologies designed and made by Chinese manufacturing enterprises.

Data by the Ministry of Industry and Information Technology (MIIT) indicates that nearly 90 Chinese manufacturing enterprises had by 2021 filed a joint application for the establishment of National Integrated Circuit Standardization Technical Committee and even made a proposition to head the secretariat at the China Electronics Standardization Institute. Examples of these manufacturers include HiSilicon, Huawei, SMIC, Xiaomi, Unichip Microelectronics, Datang Semiconductor, Zhanrui Communication, ZTE, Datang Mobile, China Mobile, Tencent, and China Unicom. Such realities indicate that standardization reform in China is at risk of getting stuck, which could in turn jeopardize plans to meet the country's SDG9 goals (Ziegler, 2016). In spite of such measures, related analyses indicate that this could still be a tricky position for China since the manufacturing sector is largely reliant on access to technologies from Western countries. Besides, China is densely populated by small-scale manufacturing enterprises, which have relatively small way in negotiating for standardization (Shen et al., 2020).

At any rate, it becomes evident that the Chinese government has set grand targets with its standardization system, which will in turn become a key pillar in facilitating the manufacturing sector's innovation power. These imply that China will need to learn to cooperate in setting up and determining standards for industry 4.0

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with international competitors. According to Ziegler (2016), this would call for sensitivity for both local and industry manufacturers. An additional major challenge comes from the fact that China has attempted to pursue numerous standardization activities that are highly disconnected from other parts of the world. In such an instance, a review of related international standards, as Ziegler (2016) observes, would not help in addressing the problem. Rather, it would demand for the “active engagement and participation of Chinese industry globally.” This is particularly interesting given that China has continued to maintain parallel compulsory and voluntary standards. The compulsory standards are expected to replace technical regulations, in spite of identifiable disadvantages like compulsory standards involve. Conversely, voluntary standards could be expected to become innovative by means of decoupling from a majority of current government controls (Ziegler, 2016).

An underlying concern is that such tendencies are contradictory, making it unclear how the system would function in practice (Shen et al., 2020). A major issue that relates to the Chinese standardization system has, however, remained unaddressed. In effect, there appears to be a lack of a comprehensive framework of technical regulations, which could effectively encourage standardisation. This has made the implementation of a complicated the capacity to implement contemporary risk - based approach. This has only served to allow the continued application of outdated systems, which are not aligned with national transition to industry 4.0. It has also made the government to be disproportionately responsible for safety and quality standards of goods and services. The implication of this trend is the intensity of accentuated compulsory controls. However, the compulsory controls applied time consuming structures that have only added to the cost of production. Such realities indicate that standardization reform in China is at risk of getting stuck, which could in turn jeopardize plans to meet the country’s SDG9 goals (Ziegler, 2016).

Yet, attempting a revision of the standards will affect China’s national transition to industry 4.0 as well as influence international standardization. The main motivation for undertaking a review of the standards is to assist in strengthening the country’s innovative power on its pathway to attain sustainable development. Ziegler (2016) suggests that for faster transition to Industry 4.0 like Germany, China should consider using a top - down driven cooperation approach, whereby standardisation is conceived from the top before being passed down to small-scale enterprises. Additionally, consideration should be given to the conceptualization of early cooperation agreements with countries that have already attained industry 4.0, such as Germany.

In any case, there are sets of reports also indicating that China has been making progress in terms of standardisation reforms to attain sustainable development goals. For instance, a report by the World Bank Group (2019) indicates that the Chinese government has already adopted sets of standards that are targeted at the green transformation and sustainable development. For instance, the National Development and Reform Commission (NDRC), the Ministry of Ecology and Environment (MEE), and the Ministry of Industry and Information Technology (MIIT) have set up standards and criteria assessing eco-industrial parks (EIPs).

Theme 3: Chinese enterprises’ innovative capacity and transition to industry 4.0

A review of research on China’s industrial policy and manufacturing development also demonstrates a focus on factors that could support a speedy transition of the manufacturing sector. While there are some concerns regarding the state of China’s industrial innovation and upgrading, it is also evident that not much

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has been written regarding leveraging innovative capacity to ensure transition to sustainable industry, innovations, and infrastructure (Shen et al., 2020). Nevertheless, it becomes evident from reviewing accessible data from China's policy research that in the past three decades, China has experienced high growth rate and high savings/investment rate. A review of policy briefs for China's structural and innovation change reveal that the country's structural transformation has aimed to high economic growth rate of more than 7% GDP/year.

A vital component of China's structural shift has, over the years, included growing the country's high value added and high technology industries. As elaborated from a review of the manufacturing sector by Green and Stern (2014), the Chinese government has appeared to mainly champion seven "strategic emerging industries." The most cited ones include biotechnology, advanced equipment manufacture, next generation information technology, energy efficient and environmental technologies, new-energy vehicles, new energy, and new materials (Shen et al., 2020). Green and Stern (2014) observed that to increase the number of high-tech industries, it is critical for China to improve its innovative capacity and investment climate. In the context of sustainable development, having the right policy mix, according to Green and Stern (2014), is crucial to encouraging low-carbon innovation. This is ideally because carbon prices and a strengthened innovative capacity would offer powerful incentives for attaining sustainable development (Green, F. & Stern, 2014). Critically, an efficient low-carbon innovation strategy will need to integrate two harmonizing sets of policy instruments. The first set consists of policies, regulation, and prices affecting GHG externalities. The next set of policies consists of those that are linked to encouraging innovation and investment in R&D. It can be construed from policy analysis of China's innovation and structural change frameworks that there are attempts to integrate the two sets of policies have (Green, F. & Stern, 2014).

For China to be successful in directing its rising technological advancement toward breakthrough innovations, particularly in low-carbon energy, it first needs to grow institutional, strategic, financial, cultural, and managerial conditions that can support such innovation. For instance, China would need to create well-funded research laboratories that are backed up by long-term research strategies, which could encourage collaboration between academic institutions and R&D centres owned by enterprises to ensure innovation. For instance, when it comes to energy innovation, such research laboratories or institutions would be much more effective if entrenched within energy innovation clusters offering favourable financial and legal environments, and "innovation ecosystem" to encourage collaboration between researchers, venture capitalists, and entrepreneurs.

It also emerges from a review of accessible industry documents that the materialization of pertinent policies for supporting the growth of high-end manufacturing industry has recently become the focal point of policy research. In one such review, Li and Liu (2019) elaborates that on the pathway to attaining industry 4.0, developing an advanced manufacturing industry with focus on innovation is critical. Li and Liu (2019) looked at the spatial characteristics of the efficiency of China's technological innovation and how it is linked to environmental regulations. Their findings suggested that technological levels in rural areas or at the provincial level are imbalanced. Voluntary regulations have had a positive effect on the efficiency of technological innovation, even as mandatory regulation did not have a significant effect (Green, F. & Stern, 2014). A number of observations can be made from reviewing published literature on the state of innovation in light of the drive to sustainable development reveals that the country's innovation potential in the manufacturing sector is yet to be regarded as sufficiently robust to support transition to industry 4.0. It can also be observed

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that the manufacturing sector is presently at the low end of the value chain. There are also concerns as regards the low efficiency of production, leading to low product quality (Li and Liu, 2019).

Li and Liu (2019) believe that China's low-cost advantage as far as the manufacturing sector is concerned is slowly but surely weakening, which in turn contributed the weakened added value of products. Li and Liu (2019) blamed the current state of such realities to weak collaborative innovation. Related studies have also looked at China's open innovation (OI), particularly how it affects manufacturer's innovation capabilities and performance. For instance, Zhang et al. (2015) carried out a survey of 119 firms in South China and established that introverted and extroverted open innovation activities positively affect manufactures' innovation performance (Li & Liu, 2019). On the other hand, f manufactures' potential absorptive capacities negatively affect their introverted open innovation activities although they also positively affect their extroverted open innovation activities. Even so, government policy was found to have played a divergent role in the process of open innovation that affects manufactures' performance. In effect, tax and fiscal policies were found to substantially affect introverted open innovation, even as property rights policies had more significant effect on extroverted open innovation (Green, F. & Stern, 2014).

A review of research on China's industrial policy and manufacturing development also demonstrates a focus on factors that could support a speedy transition of the manufacturing sector. There are definite concerns regarding the state of China's industrial innovation and upgrading. Indeed, a review of research on industrial innovation and upgrading of manufacturing sector reveal a need for policies that can leverage China's innovative capacity to ensure transition to sustainable industry, innovations, and infrastructure (Li & Liu, 2019).

There is some evidence of the materialization of germane policies for supporting the development of high-end manufacturing industry that are synonymous with industry 4.0 and in turn enhancing China's competitiveness in the international market. According to Li and Liu (2019), in the process of transitioning to industry 4.0, at the centre of developing a strong manufacturing is built in the transition to industry 4.0, placing emphasis on enhancing the country's advanced manufacturing industry, and putting up structures that can encourage innovation in the manufacturing sector.

In the attempt to evaluate innovation efficiency, Sun and Wang used a three-level by using "evaluation index system of industrial gross output value, total investment of scientific research funds, investment intensity of scientific research funds, and proportion of sales revenue." This enabled their study to examine the issue of innovation from different perspectives, such as innovation input ability, potential innovation ability, and innovation output ability (Foreman-Peck, 2013; Cho et al., 2017; Liu 2014). They observed that the key factors influencing business model innovation, such as human resources, culture, government policy, market pressures, and organizational capability demonstrated the potential for China-based high-end equipment manufacturers. These high-end equipment manufacturers could in turn improve the industry's competitiveness and performance by improving their innovative capacity.

In a related study, Li and Liu (2019) looked at the innovation efficiency of high-end manufacturing sub-sector, and established that the innovation efficiency of rural areas tended to be lower than those in urban areas, mainly because urban areas have more factors that influence innovation efficiency. Yang and Cao Hui looked at level of technological innovation in higher education institutions in China in the period 2011-2015 and established that R&D personnel's innovative capacity should be enhanced to meet internationalization efficiency.

Theme 4: Digitization of rural manufacturing sector and effects on industry 4.0

The rural manufacturing sector in China experiences numerous challenges that stand in the way of national transition to sustainable industry, innovations, and infrastructure. According to Zhang and Zhang (2020), this, in itself, indicates that the sustainability of rural areas will continue to face challenges in China. Even so, there is an indication across policy research that China has made some progress courtesy of the measures by the government to construct smart villages to encourage a realization of sustainable development of rural areas. According to Zhang and Zhang (2020), smart village consists of a rural development model that entirely makes use of ICT solutions to encourage sustainable development of rural areas, including manufacturing enterprises situated in rural areas. This is the case, given that the concept of sustainable development is concerned with benefits to the economy, society, and environment (Zheng & Zhong, 2010). Building on this understanding, the Chinese government made a proposition to implement the Rural Revitalization Strategy in 2017 and later in 2018 conceptualized the “National Rural Revitalization Strategic Plan (2018–2022)” to facilitate sustainable development in rural areas by encouraging informatization (Zhang, & Zhang, 2020).

In spite of such measures, there is strong evidence that China’s rural areas experience significant challenges that are delaying the realization of sustainable development. The first challenge is linked to rural to urban migration, which is rife in the country (Jia et al., 2020). This leads to brain drain in China’s rural areas. For instance, China’s urbanization rate stood at around 61% at the end of 2020. This implies that rural areas are left with less talents and skills to pursue innovation with the view of attaining industry 4.0 (Li & Liu, 2019). Another major challenge that delays sustainable development in rural China include the high economic disparity between rural and urban area, particularly as people in rural areas face extreme levels of poverty. Data reveal that the income growth rate of individuals in rural China is slow, which in turn mirrors the lagging development of the agriculture and manufacturing sectors in rural areas (Zhang, & Zhang, 2020).

A general lack of adequate skilled workforce in rural China also delays the attainment of sustainable development by manufacturing enterprises in the country (Jia et al., 2020). This is also related to the fact that traditional agricultural operations and small-scale manufacturing enterprises with comparatively low production efficiencies dominate the rural areas. A major implication of this is that the country’s fourth industrial revolution in the rural areas faces major barriers. In turn, rural manufacturing has primarily functioned as a source of raw materials for urban-based manufacturing enterprises’ industrial revolution (Li, & Liu, 2019). When it comes to factors that affect innovation, a number of studies that investigated the sustainability of small-scale manufacturers from different angles, such as social responsibility and ownership concentration also made some revelation. For instance, Jia et al. (2020), established that vicious competition in the marketplace has strengthened the negative correlation between ownership concentration and the sustainability of small-scale manufacturers’ innovation capability (Li & Liu, 2019).

With this in mind, it could be suggested that small-scale manufacturers in rural China should advance the positive effects of social responsibility on their sustainable development by means of improved innovation capabilities and personnel training (Jia et al., 2020). Indeed, as deduced from Jia’s et al. (2020) findings, small-scale manufacturers in rural China may own fewer R&D activities, although the ratio of non-R&D innovation is relatively high. In the context of China, Jia et al. (2020) centred on the impact of non-R&D innovation activities on sustainable innovation among rural manufacturers. They established that non-R&D

innovation activities tend to negatively affect manufacturers' performance, which could be cut down to a minimum in a proper threshold.

5. Discussion

In this section, the Institutional Theory is applied to explore why China's manufacturing enterprises should give in to coercive pressure and normative pressure to improve their unit labour output of China using science and technology for a faster transition to sustainable industry 4.0. This section also demonstrates why giving in to both normative and coercive pressures will enable the country to perfect their standard systems of industrialization as well as leverage its enterprises' innovative capacity to ensure a smooth and speedy transition to sustainable industry, innovations, and infrastructure. The dimensions of institutional theory, such as mimetic pressures and conventional pressures are also applied to show how digital infrastructure can enable the country's rural manufacturing sector to facilitate a faster transition to SDG9.

Institutional Theory provided a suitable theoretical lens for identifying and examining factors that promote survival and legitimacy of manufacturing enterprises' practices. From a review of documentary evidence, some of the key factors include social environment, government regulations, international conventions, culture, and economic incentives that legitimize manufacturing practices (Baumol et al., 2009; Lai et al., 2006). In the context of Chinese manufacturing companies' role in the national transition towards sustainable industry, innovations, and infrastructure, it was significant to explore factors that have legitimized how Chinese manufacturers develop the unit labour output through science and technology in order to facilitate national transition to industry 4.0, legitimization standard systems of industrialization, factors that have legitimized China's innovative capacity to speed up transition, and factors that have influenced digitization of infrastructure in the rural manufacturing sector (Schumpeter, 2002).

Legitimacy denotes the adoption of sustainable practices that key stakeholders in the manufacturing sector view to be appropriate. Essentially, the theory is concerned with how manufacturing enterprises can better secure their positions and legitimacy by adhering to regulatory structures, governmental agencies, professional critiques, and scripts and other societal and cultural practices that exert conformance pressures (Yang, 2013). Indeed, it emerges from this study that external political, social, and economic pressures are presently influencing manufacturing enterprises' strategies and organizational decision-making in their attempt to take on legitimate sustainable development practices. In exploring their legitimizing their practices, the roles of the enterprises in promoting China's national transition towards sustainable industry, innovations, and infrastructure became more evident.

6.1 Coercive pressures

In the context of the institutional theory, coercive pressures are influences wielded by powerful organizations or entities in a network to bring about change (Grewal and Dharwadkar 2002). An analysis of China's efforts to digitize the rural manufacturing sector with the view of meeting the targets for SDG9 demonstrate that there will be a need to rely substantially on coercive pressures to effect positive change. This is because the rural manufacturing sector in the country experiences numerous challenges that stand in the way of a speedy national transition to sustainable industry, innovations, and infrastructure (Zhang and Zhang,

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2020). Key challenges remain high economic disparity between rural and urban area, and rural to urban migration, which is rife in the country, which leads to brain drain in China's rural areas (Jia et al., 2020; (Li & Liu, 2019). Critically, therefore, a general lack of adequate skilled workforce in rural China could delay the attainment of sustainable development by manufacturing enterprises in the country.

This is a strong indicator that the rural manufacturing sector could delay the country's transitional efforts. In effect, there is an indication across policy research that China has only managed to make a relative progress on account of the measures put forth by the government to construct smart villages to encourage a realization of sustainable development of rural areas (Li et al., 2016; Hou et al, 2019; Zheng &Zhong, 2010). The Chinese government also seeks to implement the Rural Revitalization Strategy (RRS) in 2017 and later in 2018 conceptualized the "National Rural Revitalization Strategic Plan (NRRSP) (2018–2022)" to facilitate sustainable development in rural areas by encouraging informatization (Zhang, & Zhang, 2020). These indicate the significance of coalescing coercive power.

Leveraging Chinese manufacturers' labour output to meet sustainable development will largely depend on the quality of coercive power from the Chinese government and external agencies (Sailer, 2014; Shao, 2017). This is because it emerges from content analysis that the country's labour market reforms are largely tied to the comprehensive, Third-Plenum Reform Blueprint (TPRB) of 2013. However, the blueprint seems to have mainly focused on the economic, social, and environmental benefits from the sector's output. The government will need to restructure the labour sector to support long-term sustainable growth by bridging continually emerging skills gaps by raising the quality of education to specifically match the skills gaps. This is critical since, in spite of the government's drive for sustainability, the manufacturing sector has relatively a low number of comparative advantages as it is sensitive to costs of labour due to the high wages associated with high skilled labour and high cost of technological capital associated with industry 4.0 (Li et al., 2020).

The Chinese manufacturing enterprises will also need to give in to pressures from external entities like UNIDO, which acknowledges the significance of skills development as major driver of Industry 4.0. This could enable China's manufacturing enterprises to undergo a pro-active skills transformation with emphasis on shaping the young generation to be "robotic natives" and to enable the manufacturing industry to meet the skills requirements for industry 4.0 (Yang, 2013, Sailer, 2014; Shao, 2017).

The Chinese manufacturing enterprises will also need to give in to pressures from the United Nations Commission on Sustainable Development (CSD), which emphasises sustainable economic development by improving production, economic development, and economic structures (Li et al. 2018). Employing measures recommended by CSD would compel China to pursue the process of industry upgrading to ensure sustainable economic development presents an effective approach for improving the efficiency of production processes, reduction of carbon emissions, and energy saving. Related studies have also linked low-carbon industries to green industries (Beier et al., 2018; Gabriel and Pessl, 2016).

Coercive power from the Chinese government and external agencies is also found as having a strong potential to improve enable the manufacturing industry-standard systems with the view of speeding up a transition to Industry 4.0. The matter of industry standards has, in particular, been emphasized by the United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO), which acknowledges that a transition to sustainable Industry 4.0 technologies can only be attained once individual technologies, formats, and interfaces are standardised (Beier et al., 2018; Cerri et al., 2016; Ferrera et al, 2017). This indicates an absolute need for China to consolidate new concepts through consensus-based standardization at initial stages of technological

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innovation prior to being adopted in manufacturing activities globally. In which case, there is a need to accelerate new standards that can enable or facilitate the acceleration to industry 4.0 by making sure that new standards are developed that can be pursued by various countries (Abramova & Grishchenko, 2020; Deloitte, 2018). As established, standardization is crucial for guaranteeing interoperability between varied modules of Industry 4.0 production lines as it enables technology providers to engage in collaborative research and production systems, as well as present innovators with a chance to create and test how components from different manufacturers interact (Weyer et al., 2015).

6.2 Normative pressures

In the context of the institutional theory, normative pressures are influences exerted by the overwhelming effects of professionalization, professional networks, and formal education on organizational practices (Grewal and Dharwadkar 2002). It is confirmed in this documentary analysis that while China has an education system that supports the industrial economy, the relatively broad skills gaps delay the transition to Industry 4.0 because of concerns related to quality output. This leads to the realization that China country still needs to overcome the challenge to delivering requisite skills for a post-industrial economy (Woetzel et al., 2021). Therefore, for the country's manufacturing enterprises to facilitate faster transition to industry 4.0, they will need to focus on digitization and robotization in the. They also need to advance and refresh their skills to meet evolving occupations (Woetzel et al., 2021). It also emerged that care should be taken to ensure that transitional process to industry 4.0 does not overlook the strategic evolution of manufacturing enterprises with regard to leveraging a highly technological advanced labour to facilitate value creation. It also develops from this analysis that small-scale manufacturers in rural China should advance the positive effects of social responsibility on their sustainable development by means of improved innovation capabilities and personnel training (Jia et al., 2020).

Manufacturing enterprises will also need to give in to normative pressures to ensure that there is a broad understanding and incorporation of industry-standard systems on transition to Industry 4.0. For China, there appears to be a lack of a comprehensive framework of technical regulations, which could effectively encourage standardisation. Yet, any attempt to revise the standards will affect China's national transition to industry 4.0 as well as influence international standardization (Yang, 2013, Sailer, 2014; Shao, 2017). At any rate,, the idea of setting up industry standards for technology innovation has been found to have intrinsic value with respect to enabling interoperability among Industry 4.0 technological innovations and their universal usability (Shen et al., 2020; Ziegler, 2016). Still, it is established in the research that the issue of standardisation is a challenge for China, particularly as representatives from Western countries dominate international panels. This implies the need to develop greater professional networks to influence international panels, as this would make sure that designing of standards are aligned with the technologies designed and made by Chinese manufacturing enterprises. These imply a need for China to learn to cooperate in setting up and determining standards for industry 4.0 with international competitors.

6.3 Mimetic pressures

In the context of the institutional theory, mimetic pressures occur when organizations, as a result of uncertainty, imitate or replicate the practices of successful competitors. In the manufacturing sector, a number

of institutional actors potentially exert pressures that influence the practices that should be legitimated (Scott 2008).

For Chinese manufacturing enterprises, a major focus area for replication includes taking on innovation and greater R&D investment to facilitate the national transition to sustainable industry 4.0. It is deduced from the documents reviewed that there are some concerns regarding the state of China's industrial innovation and speed of upgrading technology. It is also observed that not much has been written regarding leveraging innovative capacity to ensure transition to sustainable industry, innovations, and infrastructure (Shen et al., 2020). It is critical for Chinese enterprises to improve their innovative capacity and investment climate by imitating their competitors in the developed world in order to be more competitive. As evident from the situation in Germany, having the right policy mix is crucial to facilitating low-carbon innovation. In effect, carbon prices and a strengthened innovative capacity could provide the enterprises with greater incentives to attain sustainable development (Yang, 2013, Sailer, 2014; Shao, 2017). As it emerges from the situation in developed nations, an efficient low-carbon innovation strategy for Chinese enterprises would call for an integration of two harmonizing sets of policy instruments. The first set consists of policies, regulation, and prices affecting GHG externalities. The next set of policies consists of those that are linked to encouraging innovation and investment in R&D (Green, F. & Stern, 2014). Lastly, China also needs to create well-funded research laboratories that are backed up by long-term research strategies, which could encourage collaboration between academic institutions and R&D centres owned by enterprises to ensure innovation.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

7.1 Conclusion

Heightened collective coercive pressure from the Chinese government and external environmental standardisation agencies reduces conflicts in social and economic logic, thus lowering the propensity for Chinese manufacturing enterprises to delay the transition to a sustainable industry 4.0. For China to fully digitize the rural manufacturing sector in order to meet the targets for SDG9, there will be a need to rely substantially on coercive pressures to effect positive changes like improving digital infrastructure and education. This is because the rural manufacturing sector in the country experiences challenges like high economic disparity between rural and urban area, and rural to urban migration, leading to a general lack of adequate skilled workforce to facilitate the transition. The Chinese manufacturing enterprises will also need to give in to pressures from external agencies that emphasises sustainable economic development by improving production, economic development, and economic structures. This could compel China to pursue the process of industry upgrading to ensure sustainable economic development presents an effective approach for improving the efficiency of production processes, reduction of carbon emissions, and energy saving. Related studies have also linked low-carbon industries to green industries. Coercive power from the Chinese government and external agencies could also help elevate the manufacturing industry-standard systems to speed up a transition to Industry 4.0.

Heightened mimetic pressure from increased competition for sustainable products in the international market has also reduced the propensity for Chinese manufacturing enterprises to delay the transition to a sustainable industry 4.0. For Chinese manufacturing enterprises, a major focus area for replication includes

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taking on innovation and greater R&D investment to facilitate the national transition to sustainable industry 4.0. It is critical for Chinese enterprises to improve their innovative capacity and investment climate by imitating their competitors in the developed world in order to be more competitive.

Heightened normative pressure through education and training has increased the social logic and reduced the propensity for Chinese manufacturing enterprises to concentrate on profit logic. While China has an education system that supports the industrial economy, the relatively broad skills gaps have delayed the transition to Industry 4.0 because of concerns related to quality output. For the country's manufacturing enterprises to facilitate faster transition to industry 4.0, they will need to focus on digitization and robotization in the. They also need to advance and refresh their skills to meet evolving occupations. Manufacturing enterprises will also need to give in to normative pressures to ensure that there is a broad understanding and incorporation of industry-standard systems on transition to Industry 4.0. For China, there appears to be a lack of a comprehensive framework of technical regulations, which could effectively encourage standardisation. Yet, any attempt to revise the standards will affect China's national transition to industry 4.0 as well as influence international standardization.

7.2 Recommendations

As a source of coercive pressure, the Chinese government should vigorously develop science and technology as well as take the advantage of industrial 4.0 as a mechanism for improving unit labour output. To realize SDG 9, manufacturing firms should aim to overcome resource constraints, build, and strengthen their innovative capacities, and explore innovative means for resolution of underlying development challenges. China also needs to instil a "new national ethos of lifelong learning." Yet, this is not unique to China.

The Chinese government will need to restructure the labour sector to support long-term sustainable growth by bridging continually emerging skills gaps by raising the quality of education to specifically match the skills gaps.

There is also a need for China to consolidate new concepts through consensus-based standardization at initial stages of technological innovation prior to being adopted in manufacturing activities globally.

Small-scale manufacturers in rural China should advance the positive effects of social responsibility on their sustainable development by means of improved innovation capabilities and personnel training.

Having the right policy mix would also facilitate low-carbon innovation. Lastly, China also needs to create well-funded research laboratories that are backed up by long-term research strategies, which could encourage collaboration between academic institutions and R&D centres owned by enterprises to ensure innovation.

7.3 Research Limitation and Future Research recommendations

Essentially, the weaknesses of applying document analysis were not many limitations since they mainly consisted of potential concerns that needed significant awareness prior to selecting the method. An underlying concern included the fact that some documents reviewed such as incident reports, newspapers, policy manuals, research journals, and annual reports were not created with data research agendas. As a result, they required strong investigative skills. Additionally, not all the selected documents could completely supply all pertinent information needed for answering your research questions. For instance, market research reports could only offer a small quantity of practical data.

On account of the highlighted research limitations, future studies could consider using quantitative research surveys to explore mechanisms through which Chinese government could vigorously improve unit labour

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output in both the private and state-owned enterprises without being seen as coercive. Such future studies could as well investigate how the labour sector could be restructured to bridge the growing skills gaps without risking the exclusion of lowly skilled labour from participating in the national transition to industry 4.0. Research limitations also make it unclear on how manufacturing enterprises could be brought together to consolidate new concepts through consensus-based standardization at initial stages of technological innovation. This could form the core of future research. Besides, future research emphasis could be placed on the right policy mix that could facilitate low-carbon innovation..

References

- Abramova N. & Grishchenko N. ICTs, labour productivity and employment: sustainability in industries in Russia [J]. *Procedia Manufacturing*: 2020, 43: 299–305.
- Agarwal N., Gneting U. & Mhlanga R. Raising the bar: Rethinking the role of business in the sustainable development goals. *Oxfam Discussion Papers*, 2017,
- Anadon L, Chan G, Harley A, Matus K, Moon S. (Making technological innovation work for sustainable development [J]. *PNAS*: 2016, 113(35): 9682-9690.
- Bakkari M & Khatory A. Industry 4.0: Strategy for More Sustainable Industrial Development in Smes. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Operations Management*: 2017, 1693–1701.
- Baruzzi S. China’s industrial standards for the internet of things: What the draft guidelines say. *China Briefing*, 2021. Available at: <https://www.china-briefing.com/news/china-internet-of-things-industrial-standards-draft-guidelines-released-5-major-standards/>
- Baumol WJ, Litan RE, Schramm CJ. *Good capitalism, bad capitalism, and the economics of growth and prosperity*. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press, 2009.
- Baxter W. Thailand 4.0 and the future of work in the kingdom. *International Labour Organization*, 2017. Available at: https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---dgreports/---dcomm/documents/meetingdocument/wcms_549062.pdf
- Beier G, Niehoff S., & Xue X. More sustainability in industry through industrial internet of things? [J] *Applied Sciences*: 2018, 8(2): 219.
- Brettel M, Friederichsen N, Keller, M, Rosenberg, M. How Virtualization, Decentralization and Network Building Change the Manufacturing Landscape: An Industry 4.0 Perspective.[J] *International Journal of Information and Communication Engineering*: 2014, 8(1): 37–44.
- Cerri D, Terzi S. Proposal of a toolset for the improvement of industrial systems’ lifecycle sustainability through the utilization of ICT technologies [J]. *Computers in Industry*: 2014, 81: 47–54.
- Charles E, Zabala-Iturriagoitia, JM. Public Procurement for Innovation as mission-oriented innovation policy. *Res. Policy*: 2012, 41: 1757–1769.
- Cho C, Park S, Son J, Lee S. Comparative analysis of R&D-based innovation capabilities in SMEs to design innovation policy [J]. *Sci. Public Policy* 2017, 44, 403–416.
- De Man J, Strandhagen, J. An Industry 4.0 research agenda for sustainable business models. *Procedia CIRP*: 2017, 63: 721–726.
- DEG. Bridging the skills gaps in China: Hape Holding AG – A sustainable toy manufacturer fosters youth apprenticeship and the development of its suppliers, 2016. Available at: https://www.deginvest.de/DEG-Documents-in-English/About-us/What-is-our-impact/Case-Study_Hape-Holding-AG_EN_2016-02.pdf
- Deloitte. Preparing tomorrow’s workforce for the Fourth Industrial Revolution For business: A framework for action. *Deloitte*, 2018. Available at: <https://www2.deloitte.com/content/dam/Deloitte/global/Documents/About-Deloitte/gx-preparing-tomorrow-workforce-for-4IR.pdf>
- Ferrera E, Rossini R, Baptista AEvans S, Hovest G et al. Toward industry 4.0: Efficient and sustainable manufacturing leveraging MAESTRI Total Efficiency Framework [J]. *Sustainable Design and Manufacturing*: 2017, 68(c): 624–633.
- Foreman-Peck J. Effectiveness and efficiency of SME innovation policy [J]. *Small Bus. Econ*: 2013, 41: 55–70.
- Freeman C. *Technology, policy, and economic performance: Lessons from Japan*; Pinter Publishers: London, UK; New York, NY, USA, 1987; p. 155.
- Gabriel M, Pessl E. Industry 4.0 and Sustainability Impacts: Critical Discussion of Sustainability Aspects with a Special Focus [J]. *International Journal of Engineering*: 2016, 14(2): 131–137.

International Journal of Research Publications Vol 1, No 3, 2022 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19706933

- García-Muiña F, Medina-Salgadpo M, Ferrari A, Cucchi M. Sustainability Transition in Industry 4.0 and Smart Manufacturing with the Triple-Layered Business Model Canvas [J]. *Sustainability*: 2020, 12: 2364
- Gerlitz L. Design Management as a Domain of Smart and Sustainable Enterprise: Business Modelling for Innovation and Smart Growth in Industry 4.0 [J]. *Entrepreneurship and Sustainability Issues*: 2016, 3(3): 244–268.
- Global Skills Summit. Skill development for industry 4.0. BRICS Skill Development Working Group, 2016
- Green F, Stern N. An innovative and sustainable growth path for China: a critical decade. Centre for Climate Change Economics and Policy Grantham Research Institute on Climate Change and the Environment, 2014.
- Grewal R, Dharwadkar R. The role of the institutional environment in marketing channels. *Journal of Marketing*: 2002, 66(3): 82–97
- Hanson A. Ecological Civilization in the People’s Republic of China: Values, Action, and Future Needs. ADB East Asia Working Paper Series, No. 21, 2019.
- Hou J, Chen J, Song H, Wang G. Are Non-R&D Innovation Activities Actually Effective for Innovation Sustainability? Empirical Study from Chinese High-Tech Industry [J]. *Sustainability*: 2019, 11: 174.
- Huq F, Stevenson M. Implementing socially sustainable practices in challenging institutional contexts: Building theory from seven developing country supplier cases [J]. *Journal of Business Ethics*: 2020, 161:415–442.
- IISD. How can progress on infrastructure, industry and innovation contribute to achieving the SDGs? Policy Briefs, 2017. <https://sdg.iisd.org/commentary/policy-briefs/how-can-progress-on-infrastructure-industry-and-innovation-contribute-to-achieving-the-sdgs/>
- Jia C, Tang X & Kan Z. Does the nation innovation system in China support the sustainability of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) Innovation? [J]. *Sustainability*: 2020, 12:118-127.
- Khan AM, Manopichetwattana V. Models for distinguishing innovative and noninnovative small firms [J]. *J. Bus. Ventur*: 1989, 4, 187–196.
- Kumar N., Hammill M., Raihan S. & Panda S. Strategies for achieving the sustainable development goals (SDGs) in South Asia: Lessons from policy simulations. *South and South-West Asia Development Papers* 1601, 2016.
- Lai KH, Wong CW, Cheng TC. Institutional isomorphism and the adoption of information technology for supply chain management [J]. *Computers in Industry*: 2006, 57(1): 93–98.
- Lasi H, Fettke P, Kemper H, Feld T, Hoffmann M. Industry 4.0. *Business & Information Systems Engineering*. *Business & Information Systems Engineering*: 2014, 6(4): 239–242 (2014).
- Leng S. & Lee A. China’s goal of productivity growth faster than the overall economy hinges on rural education, innovation. *South China Morning Post*, 2021. Available at: <https://www.scmp.com/economy/china-economy/article/3125212/chinas-goal-productivity-growth-faster-overall-economy-hinges>
- Li H., Sheng Y. & Ding Y. Research on the Institutional Influence on the Development of the High-Tech Industry. *Digital Object Identifier*: 2020, 8: 1-8.
- Li J, Yang B, Pan Z. Ownership concentration of SMEs, product market competition and sustainability of enterprise innovation [J]. *China Sci. Technol. Forum*: 2016, 5: 59–64.
- Li P, Liu, Y. The development of scientific and technological research system in German and its implications to the innovation base construction in China. *Sci Manag Res*: 2011, 2: 52–57.
- Li Q, Liu T. Innovation efficiency of China’s high-end manufacturing industry: Evidence from Super-SBM Model and Malmquist Index [J]. *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*: 2019, 1.
- Liu, F. Research on the Development Status and Policies of China’s Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises—Research on the Transformation and Upgrade of Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises in the New Situation. *Contemp. Econ [J]. Manag*: 2014, 36: 9–18.
- Lundvall BÅ. *National System of Innovation: Towards a Theory of Innovation and Interactive Learning*; Pinter Publishers: London, UK, 1992; p. 317.
- Machado C, Winroth M, da Silva E. Sustainable manufacturing in Industry 4.0: an emerging research agenda [J]. *International Journal of Production Research*: 2019, 58(5): 1462-1484.
- Mensah J, Casadevall S. Sustainable development: Meaning, history, principles, pillars, and implications for human action: Literature review [J]. *Cogent Social Sciences*: 2019, 5(1): 1-21.
- Müller J, Voig K. Sustainable industrial value creation in SMEs: A Comparison between Industry 4.0 and Made in China 2025 [J]. *International Journal Of Precision Engineering And Manufacturing-Green Technology*: 2018, 5(5): 659-670
- Oreglia, E. ICT and (personal) development in rural China [ICTs for Leisure in Development Special issue [J]. *Information Technologies & International Development*: 2014, 10(3): 19–30.
- Prakash A. Infrastructure and Industrialisation: Ensuring Sustainable and Inclusive Growth in Africa. *ERIA No.* 2018-02,
- Randall L, Vestergård O, Meijer M. Rural perspectives on digital innovation: Experiences from small enterprises in the Nordic countries

and Latvia. Nordregio Report 2020:4

- Saastamoinen J, Reijonen H, Tammi T. Should SMEs pursue public procurement to improve innovative performance? [J]. *Technovation*: 2018, 69: 2–14.
- Sailer J. M2M-Internet of Things-Web of Things-Industry 4.0. e & i Elektrotechnik und Informationstechnik: 2014, 131(1): 3–4.
- Sarkar A. Promoting eco-innovations to leverage sustainable development of eco-industry and green growth [J]. *European Journal of Sustainable Development*: 2013, 2(1):171-224.
- Schumpeter JA. Chapter 7-The Economy as a Whole, English translation of *Das Gesamtbild der Volkswirtschaft*. In *Theorie der wirtschaftlichen Entwicklung*; Schumpeter, J.A., Ed.; Blank: Oxford, UK, 2002; Volume 9, pp. 93–145.
- Scott WR. Approaching adulthood: The maturing of institutional theory. *Theory and Society*: 2008, 37(5): 427–442.
- Shao A. The study on comparison between ‘China’s Manufacture 2015’ & ‘Industry 4.0’ and countermeasures to promote [J]. *J Shanghai Econ Manag Coll*: 2017; 15(2): 36–42.
- Shen Z, Siraj A, Jiang H, Zhu Y, Ji J. Chinese-Style Innovation and Its International Repercussions in the New Economic Times [J]. *Sustainability*: 2020, 2:1-17.
- Standards Australia. Industry 4.0: An Australian perspective: recommendations report to Australian Government – Department of industry, innovation and science, 2017. Available at: <https://www.standards.org.au/getmedia/29653164-cd4d-43f0-9afc-e8db58710f2e/Industry-4-0-Recommendations-Report.pdf.aspx>
- Stock T, Obenaus M, Kunz M, Kunz S, Kohl H. Industry 4.0 as enabler for a sustainable development: A qualitative assessment of its ecological and social potential. *process safety and environmental protection*, 2018, 1-19.
- Strange R, Zucchella R. Industry 4.0, global value chains and international business. *Multinatl. Bus. Rev*: 2017, 25(3): 174–184.
- The World Bank. Guangdong, China: Training a Skilled Workforce for Industrial Upgrade. 2020. Available at: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/feature/2020/06/04/guangdong-china-training-a-skilled-workforce-for-industrial-upgrade>
- Tranfield D., Denyer D., & Smart P. Towards a methodology for developing evidence-informed management knowledge by means of systematic review. *British journal of management*: 2003,14: 207–222.
- UNCTAD. Achieving the sustainable development goals in the least developed countries, 2021. Available at: https://unctad.org/system/files/official-document/aldc2018d4_en.pdf
- UNCTAD. Structural transformation, Industry 4.0 and inequality: Science, technology and innovation policy challenges, 2019. Available at: https://unctad.org/system/files/official-document/ciid43_en.pdf
- UNIDO. Industry 4.0: Opportunities and challenges of the new industrial revolution for developing countries and economies in transition, 2017. Available at: https://www.unido.org/sites/default/files/2017-01/Unido_industry-4_NEW_0.pdf
- Weyer S, Schmitt M., Ohmer M, Gorecky D. Towards Industry 4.0 - Standardization as the crucial challenge for highly modular, multi-vendor production systems [J]. *IFAC-Papers OnLine*: 2015, 48: 579–584.
- Woetzel J., Seong J., Leung N. et al. Reskilling China: Transforming the world’s largest workforce into lifelong learners. *McKinsey*, 2021. Available at: <https://www.mckinsey.com/featured-insights/china/reskilling-china-transforming-the-worlds-largest-workforce-into-lifelong-learners>
- World Bank Group. Enhancing China’s regulatory framework for eco-industrial parks, 2019. Available at: <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/bitstream/handle/10986/31572/Enhancing-China-s-Regulatory-Framework-for-Eco-Industrial-Parks-Comparative-Analysis-of-Chinese-and-International-Green-Standards.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>
- Xu G, Lin G. New thing on the transformation and upgrading of traditional manufacturing industry under the background of industry 4.0. *Shanghai. J. Econ*: 2015, 10: 107–113.
- Yang C. China’s manufacturing industry development strategy under the background of global “re-industrialization”. *J Soochow Univ Philos Soc Sci Ed*: 2013, 6, 100–105.
- Zhang X, Zhang,Z. How do smart villages become away to achieve sustainable development in rural areas? [J] *Smart Village Planning and Practices in China. Sustainability*: 2020, 12: 1-20.
- Zhang YJ. Analysis of SME technology innovation policy from the perspective of policy tools [J]. *China Adm*: 2012, 4: 43–47.
- Zhang ZG, Chen ZM, Li YJ. Research on the relationship between open innovation, absorptive capacity and innovation performance. *Sci. Res. Manag*: 2015, 36: 49–56.
- Zhao F, Liu Z. Industrial transformation strategy for the manufacturing sector of China in the tide of industry 4.0. *Forum on Science and Technology in China*: 2016, 1: 8–62.
- Zhao X, Michaelowa A. CDM potential for rural transition in china case study: Options in Yinzhou District, Zhejiang Province, HWWA Discussion Paper, No. 291, Hamburg Institute of International Economics (HWWA), Hamburg, 2004.
- Zheng, D.L.; Zhong, S.H. 30 Years of Chinese High-Tech Policy: Based on the Analysis on Policy Text. *Sci. Technol. Prog. Countermeas*. 2010, 27, 90–93.
- Ziegler K. China's global ambition to standardization – Impact on trading partners. Working Paper, East-West Center Workshop on

International Journal of Research Publications Vol 1, No 3, 2022 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19706933

Mega-Regionalism - New Challenges for Trade and Innovation, 2016.

International Journal of Research Publications Vol 1, No 3, 2022 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19706933

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